

**Plant study on the International
Space Station using hyperspectral
imaging and carbon dioxide gas
sensing technology for the growth of
healthy plant life**

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Declaration by candidate

I, Sam Ahmadzadeh, hereby declare that the work presented in this thesis is my own work and has not been submitted in part or whole, for any other degrees at this or any other University or Institute. Where other sources of information have been used, they have been acknowledged in the appropriate format.

Signature _____

Date 01/08/2023

Abstract

The project investigates the monitoring of plant growth and development in a closed system environment on board the International Space Station to compare with an Earth-based trial. The environmental sensing system developed has an LED lighting schedule to mimic day and night on earth and allows for the continuous measurement of CO₂, relative humidity and temperature in the plant environment during growth. This information is timestamped and can be stored and examined at a later stage. A non-destructive hyperspectral imaging system has been developed which uses novel sputter deposited linear variable filters combined with machine learning algorithms to extract useful information about plant species and health. Moreover, an optical broadband absorber coating has been designed and deposited that boosts the performance of a thermal detector thermopile by 220%. This produces a more sensitive final thermopile device with higher detectivity when compared with an un-coated thermopile. The results from the Earth-based study show that the monitoring system can be successful in monitoring the immediate environment and plant growth, when combined with hyperspectral imaging the resulting information can give insights into plant health and identification. The combined system can be used to find the optimal conditions for plant growth and development stages. Moreover, a combined system using hyperspectral imaging, CO₂ gas and environmental humidity and temperature sensing could be a valuable measurement

instrument in deep-space exploration or on a Space station, where plant cultivation is vital to the overall mission success.

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Preface

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Thesis overview

The schematic diagram below outlines the project and relates each section to relevant chapters.

Figure 1: Overview of the project with sections detailing to chapters.

The following sections provide an overview of the contents of each chapter.

Chapter 1

Chapter One outlines the background and motivations of the project and provides considerations for launching an experiment into Space. The objectives and expected outcomes are also defined.

Chapter 2

In Chapter Two, a brief history of thin films and an introduction to optical filtering is given. The thin film deposition technique and microwave plasma-assisted deposition system are also explored, along with substrate preparation methods and metrology techniques used for analysis.

Chapter 3

Chapter Three presents the single-layer work and analysis carried out and based upon this the design and discussion of a specialised optical filter. The chapter ends with the characterisation of the specialised linear variable filter and a comparison of designed to fabricated spectral profiles.

Chapter 4

Within Chapter Four an introduction to hyperspectral imaging and its application is given. The assembly and testing of a prototype hyperspectral imaging camera utilising a linear variable filter approach are presented, along with the comparison to a commercially available high-end system. The chapter finishes with the prototype camera testing out in the field and the results of algorithm development.

Chapter 5

The chapter focuses on an investigation into the performance enhancement of a thermal sensor used as a potential mid-infrared detector within a non-dispersive infrared gas sensor. A broadband carbon absorber coating is designed, modelled and optimised for use on the photosensitive area of a thermopile device. The chapter then goes into two sub-investigations of thin-film absorptance and stress. Based on the sub-investigation results, an optimised design is proposed which leads to a significant boost in the thermopile output.

Chapter 6

This Chapter introduces NDIR gas sensing principles and the detection of CO₂ using different types of emitters and detectors. A comparison is then made between an in-house built sensor and a gas sensor available from industry. The performances of both sensors are evaluated and conclusions are drawn on which is most appropriate for the space-based CO₂ environment plant study.

Chapter 7

The chapter outlines the major considerations and constraints of space-based experimentation, specifically contamination and safety risks for the plant study. Furthermore, the chapter covers the plant life identified for the study as well as the plant performance in the plant "hardiness" experiments. Also, the construction of the experiment box and a 7-day test trial on Earth is performed, simulating conditions on board the ISS.

Chapter 8

In this chapter, the transport and launching of the experiment are detailed. The module capture and experiment setup are covered, the results are obtained from the space-based experiment and an explanation of trial results is detailed.

Chapter 9

In this chapter, the work carried out and described in previous chapters is summarised and an overall conclusion is presented with future work.

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Abbreviations

ABS acrylonitrile butadiene styrene.

ADC analogue-to-digital converter.

AR anti-reflection.

BBA broadband Absorber.

CMOS complementary metal-oxide semiconductor.

CVD chemical vapour deposition.

D* specific detectivity.

DAC digital to analogue converter.

DLC diamond-like carbon.

EM electromagnetic radiation.

FPBP Fabry-Perot bandpass.

FPGA field programmable gate array.

GSS Gas Sensing Solutions Ltd.

GUI graphical user interface.

HSI hyperspectral imaging..

HWOT half-wave optical thickness.

IoT internet of things.

IR infrared radiation.

ISS International Space Station.

ISSET International Space School Educational Trust.

LED light-emitting diode.

LEDs light-emitting diodes.

LVF linear variable filter.

LVFs Linear variable filters.

MBE molecular-beam epitaxy.

MCU microcontroller unit.

MEMS microelectromechanical systems.

NDIR non-dispersive infrared.

NG-18 NASA Commercial robotic resupply spacecraft Cygnus Northrop
Grumman 18.

PCA principal component analysis.

PD photodiode.

ppm parts per Million.

PVD physical vapour deposition.

QWOT quarter-wave optical thickness.

RH relative humidity.

RTC real time clock.

SEM scanning electron microscopy.

SNR signal-to-noise ratio.

SNV standard normal variate.

SpX-26 SpaceX Commercial Resupply Service 26.

ULP ultra low power.

WBCO wide band cut-off.

WFF Wallops Flight Facility.

Chapter 1

Background and motivation

1.1 Overview

The pioneering work carried out by Russian scientists in the 1950s (1; 2) has led to over 60 years' worth of plant-growing research in space. Throughout this time several experiments have grown plants on spacecraft, the International Space Station (ISS), and other space stations (3) and have played a unique role in human life expansion in Space. Plants grown in Space offer a number of benefits. such as carbon dioxide reduction, oxygen production and a supply of nutritious food. There are also physiological benefits with plants grown on Space stations, the presence of leafy green plants can boost astronaut attitude and reduce stress or anxiety aboard the ISS (4).

However, growing plants in Space comes with a number of unique challenges. The limited space and availability of resources, the harsh Space launch and ISS environment, and plant growth in microgravity (5). In order to overcome these challenges, a variety of techniques and technologies have been developed and tested on Earth suitable for Space use. Tech-

niques and technologies include artificial light-emitting diode (LED) lighting with narrow wavelength outputs, controlled environmental conditions, controlled growth media and monitoring systems.

A primary goal of Space-based plant-growing systems is the production and harvesting of food for astronauts on the Space station. This is also of particular importance on long-haul missions (6; 7), for example to Mars (8) or planets farther away, where freshly sourced food is extremely limited and resupply missions would not be an option (9). Prior studies have grown lettuce, tomatoes, peppers, peas, herbs and spices in Space. The studies employed a number of techniques, including hydroponics (plants grown in nutrient-rich water), aeroponics (plants grown in a nutrient-rich vapour or mist) and similar to Earth-based methods such as nutrient-rich soil or soil alternatives.

Moreover, plant growth in Space has also been a matter of scientific research (10; 11). Plant growth and development have been monitored in microgravity and the space environment (12; 13), as well as the ability of plants and plant mechanisms to adapt to the new space environment.

The research carried out will contribute to the literature related to plant growth and development in Space and overall plant biology which could have meaningful applications on Earth.

The growth, development and cultivation of plant life in Space can assist to sustain or enhance human life, providing nutrient-rich leafy green foods on long-haul missions (7) or on other planets and adding to the scientific literature and body of knowledge. Whilst there are a significant number of challenges, research on the advances of techniques or technologies has allowed plant growth in space to be successful. Deep Space exploration and Space colonisation will likely rely on Space-based grown plants; they have

a critical role to play.

1.2 Early space-based plant research

The history of plants in Space dates back many decades with several experiments focused on how plants grow and develop onboard spacecraft and Space stations in microgravity and compared with Earth-based controls. As well as practical applications of Space-based plant growth and cultivation, such as carbon dioxide reduction, oxygen generation and as a source of nutrient-rich food (14). In this section, the history of experiments growing plants in Space will be explored in more detail.

In 1959, Russian scientists conducted one of the earliest plant growth studies in Space, where seeds of various plants were launched on a biological payload (1; 2). This was among some of the earliest experiments and served as the starting point of Space-based plant growth research.

In 1966, Kosmos 110 was launched by the Soviet Union, the spacecraft was the first of its kind to conduct successful Space-based plant growth research experiments. The plants grown included cabbage and lettuce. These plants were grown from seeds and when compared to earth-based controls, showed greater overall yield. This was an extremely important milestone in space botany, as it demonstrated that plants can be grown in the Space environment (1).

In 1971, 500 tree seeds were launched on the Apollo 14 mission. The seeds were exposed to the lunar environment and brought back to Earth for germination. The germinated seeds were planted and referred to as “moon trees” (15). This experiment was among one of the first to have

seeds exposed in Space and planted back on Earth, the scientific question to be answered was if the plants exposed to the lunar environment had any effects compared with ground controls, which they did not. However, this was an important milestone in the effect of non-terrestrial environments on plant growth.

In 1973, the Skylab Space station was launched by NASA, on board the Space station experiments were set up to understand the effect of light and microgravity on rice plants. The Skylab was a major milestone in Space botany as it successfully demonstrated plants grown in a Space station and the feasibility of plants grown for practical applications, such as human consumption thus reinforcing the practical applications of Space-based plant research. The Skylab Space mission marked the first-time plants were grown in Space, not on-board spacecraft, satellites, or shuttles (16).

In 1982, Salyut 7, the Russian space station housed a micro-greenhouse module named the “biocontainer”, which grew several varieties of plants, including lettuce, tomatoes, peppers and Arabidopsis in microgravity (17; 18). The Arabidopsis was the first plant to flower in Space and the first plant to generate seeds in microgravity (19).

In 1989, the “Shuttle-Mir program” was launched by NASA, within the program several experiments on the Russian space station Mir were included to study the effects of microgravity on plant growth and development. Experiments were conducted in a miniaturised greenhouse system with controlled wavelength-specific lighting and with a plant feeding system (20; 21).

In 1995, a “Space Greenhouse” module was incorporated into the Mir program, the purpose of the module was to grow lettuce, peas and tomatoes over a prolonged period. This marked the first plant growth study over a prolonged duration in space and the results added to the development of

techniques for plant cultivation in Space (22).

In 1998, the “Astroculture” system was launched by NASA on Space Shuttle discovery, this was an experiment which grew plants in a microgravity environment. The “Astroculture” marked the first-time plants had been launched and grown on a shuttle; experimental results added to the existing techniques for plant cultivation in Space (23).

In 2001, the “Advanced Astroculture” system was launched by NASA, the system was used to grow plants on the ISS (24). That marked the first-time plants were grown on a Space Station for extended periods of time. This also marked the second time *Arabidopsis* was grown from seeds to produce seeds, “seed to seed”, in microgravity (25).

In 2014, the “Veggie” system was integrated into the ISS, which has been used to grow lettuce and other leafy green crops (26). That marked a significant milestone in the study of plants grown in Space, as a variety of plants were grown to add fresh food to astronaut diets and enhance well-being on the space station. The “Veggie” system highlighted the feasibility of fresh plants grown in space and the potential future contribution to research (27).

In summary, the growth of plants in Space has a long history and has been conducted on several different spacecraft, namely satellites, Space Shuttles and Space Stations. From the initial experiments in 1959 to the more recent veggie system on the ISS, our understanding of plant biology and the practical applications of plants in Space has greatly deepened. Whilst there are still obstacles to overcome with Space-based plant cultivation, the progress has been significant and accelerating from those initial experiments that laid the groundwork for plant growing and monitoring in Space.

1.3 Current space-based plant research

The growth, monitoring and cultivation of plants and Space is still a popular and active branch of research, with new research being conducted actively on the ISS at the moment (28). These experiments aim to deepen our understanding of space-based plant biology and to understand and overcome the challenges involved in Space-based plant growth systems. As well as widen the practical applications of Space research. Some current experiments on growing plants in space are described below in more detail.

The “Veggie” system included in the ISS in 2014 is still being used for plant-based experiments in Space and operates within a controlled gaseous and wavelength-specific lighting environment, the temperature is also controlled, and the system has successfully grown leafy green plants, tomatoes, peppers, peas and other vegetables (29).

Other than the practical application of growing nutritious crops, the “Veggie” system has also been at the forefront of plants in space scientific research, with experiments focusing on plant growth and development and competing against controls on earth to understand mechanisms of plant adaptability to microgravity (13). These experiments may have consequences on how plants are grown on earth and the potential for higher cultivation yield or more resilient plants.

A second active experiment on the ISS in space plant growth is the “Mars plant growth experiment” which is a scientific study that is attempting to simulate the conditions potentially faced by plant growth experiments on Mars (30; 31). The study simulates microgravity and space environmental factors on board the ISS to help gain a greater understanding of what is required to sustainably grow plants on other planets, which also highlights

challenges to be overcome to support human lives on other planets.

Overall, plant growth in space is a highly active area of research, with plant growth experiments currently being conducted in specialised growth chambers or micro-greenhouses on spacecraft and Space Stations, including the ISS. The experiments are conducted with the goal of better understanding plant botany and biology in microgravity. Furthermore, to explore the practical applications and challenges associated with growing plants in Space. Whilst there are still obstacles, such as the reduction in interaction opportunities, limited use of fungicides and limited power and resources, to overcome with the cultivation of plants in Space, all progress to date has been significant and plants have a critical role in deep space exploration and colonisation of distant planets.

1.4 Considerations within space-based plant research

All Space launches are incredibly challenging and involve many complex processes, both the launch itself and the experiment to be carried out must be carefully planned and tested on Earth where possible, including launching resupply missions to the ISS. Considerations must be made with the experiment design to ensure the safety of the crew on the Space Station. Other considerations such as the timing of the launch, the total cost, and the scientific outcomes of any experimentation are also vital to the experiment's success.

The scientific outcomes and goals of the experiment are key considerations, these must be clearly defined and any resources needed be available to

achieve the desired outcomes. The resources available on board the ISS are limited and it is important to understand the goals of the experiment to ensure the ISS can facilitate and meet them, this includes the equipment and crew on board, the type of research and predicted outcomes of the experiment.

The experiment design is also a key consideration when launching to the ISS. The unique challenges of launch and Space environment, such as microgravity, cold storage, temperature changes, humidity fluctuations, and the number of astronaut interactions with the experiment must be considered. This requires a high level of understanding of scientific goals and the ISS facilities available.

Safety is the most important consideration. The experiment must withstand safety standards presented by NASA to ensure the ISS crew's safety. All risks must be considered with introducing an experiment and measures in place to mitigate the overall risk to the crew and integrity of the International Space Station.

A major consideration is the cost of the experiment for the intended duration. The cost of launching one kilogram to the ISS is around \$30,000. The total cost of any scientific experiment to be launched to the ISS must fit within the available budget, including the design, experimentation and testing, the cost of the launch, the cost of the equipment and facilities on board, the cost of the astronaut's time and the cost of the disposal or return when experimentation is complete.

Finally, timing is of critical importance when launching to the ISS. The ISS has finite space for including and conducting experiments, it is important when planning the experiment to consider the crew and ISS schedule and the number of interactions available. This encompasses the availability of

required resources and the schedule of the crew to set up and carry out the experiment.

In summary, any space launch is a complex task that requires cautious planning and careful consideration of a wide range of factors. By taking all these considerations into account, the successful launch and conducting of an experiment on the ISS is achievable.

1.5 Scientific aims and expected outcomes

The scientific aims and goals within this study investigated the use of CO_2 gas, humidity, temperature sensing and hyperspectral imaging for monitoring plant growth:

1. To investigate the potential of using CO_2 gas sensing and hyperspectral imaging for monitoring plant life.
2. To study the impact on plant growth with finite CO_2 concentration.
3. To develop a real-time monitoring system that can provide information about the plant's growth and development, to optimise the conditions for long-duration space missions.
4. To use machine learning algorithms to analyse the data collected, to extract useful information about the plants' health levels and growth.
5. To compare the results obtained on the ISS with those obtained from a similar control experiment on Earth, to understand the effect of environmental conditions on plant growth.
6. To test the feasibility and reliability of the developed monitoring system and evaluate the potential of using it on future long-duration

1.5. *SCIENTIFIC AIMS AND EXPECTED OUTCOMES*

Space missions.

Chapter 2

Optical coating fabrication method

Optical coatings play a major role in many optical systems, in general, to enhance system performance by manipulating the transmission, reflection or absorption of the light. Within this study, the application is wavelength separation to achieve wavelength-separated images for hyperspectral imaging. (HSI) and to allow spectral selectivity within non-dispersive infrared gas sensors. The optical coatings used within each of the systems aimed at investigating plant growth and monitoring development are critical to project success.

2.1 Introduction

Optical coatings are applied to optical components to modify their properties - the components typically coated are mirrors, lenses, or filters. The optical coatings can be used to change the optical properties by reflecting, transmitting, or absorbing specific wavelengths of light, tailoring the optical

component to a desired application. Applications can include telescopes, cameras, and all laser systems (32).

physical vapour deposition (PVD) is a common method for the fabrication of optical thin film coatings. This technique involves the deposition of a coating material directly onto a substrate. PVD can be categorised into several subcategories, the main methods used are sputtering and thermal evaporation (33). In applications where high precision is required, PVD coatings are favoured due to the controlled nature of the deposition. However, PVD coatings can also be relatively expensive to manufacture.

Another common method of optical coating fabrication technique is chemical vapour deposition (CVD). The CVD technique involves reacting gaseous precursors to form a solid coating on the substrate (34). Unlike the PVD coatings, CVD coatings normally can be hard to control precisely, and the manufacturing method can be expensive.

To fabricate thin film optical coatings, several deposition techniques can be employed, each technique has associated advantages and disadvantages. A major focus of this study is PVD produced thin films, particularly thin films produced by a magnetron sputter deposition method.

PVD is a key deposition technique used in the semiconductor industry, where it is used to coat silicon wafers with insulating barriers and conducting materials. These built-up layers of material on silicon wafers go on to be manufactured into electronic components such as thermopiles, transistors and integrated circuitry. The PVD method is complimentary with semiconductor device fabrication due to the controlled nature of the deposition, high precision achievable and complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) compatibility (35). Electronic components typically require highly accurate thicknesses and repeatable quality to guarantee

proper functionality and the PVD technique is highly valuable.

Furthermore, the PVD technique is valuable in the optical coating industry, where it is used to deposit thin films to enhance optical properties, such as high reflectivity or high transmission, of optical components. The optical components' performance can be enhanced using PVD thin films, improving the overall performance as this deposition technique can produce uniform thin films with high precision.

Beyond the semiconductor and optical coating industries, PVD can be used to deposit wear and corrosive-resistant, hard, protective coatings to host substrates. diamond-like carbon (DLC) is a common material deposited for this purpose as it has unique properties similar to diamonds formed in nature. DLC coatings are used to reduce friction wear between mechanical parts or extend the lifespan of parts facing corrosive environments.

This investigation details the PVD sputter deposition of high-performance Linear variable filters (LVFs) and application within a hyper-spectral imaging camera and multi-gas sensor due to precise deposition thickness control and high filter transmission performance in desired wavebands. A brief history and theory of thin films are presented and the deposition system used is discussed.

2.1.1 Brief history of thin films

The history of thin films dates back at least 5,000 years when thin film coatings were first used to preserve and decorate priceless possessions by coating them in gold (36). The development and continuous improvements of vacuum technology, starting in the 1600s (36) (37), were crucial for creating the cleaner deposition settings required for the evolution of thin-

film science. With the developments continuing throughout the 1800s (36) (37), thin films gained widespread acceptance in modern life. The 1800s saw the optical coating industry dominated by multi-target sputter deposition. Additionally, first described was the characterisation of thin film structures by spectrophotometry (36). The developments in sputter deposition have seen the improvement of thin film qualities in a variety of new applications. While the name “magnetron” first appeared in print in 1921, the initial magnetron sputtering investigations were carried out in the late 1930s. Due to new techniques, better-quality thin films with improved uniformity and reproducibility were employed in practical devices such as vacuum tubes and radio receivers. Although the phrase “reactive sputtering” (variation of the sputtering process with a reactive gas introduced for both material and chemical reactions to take place) wasn’t used in the literature until 1953 (38), early metal-oxide and nitride sputtering research began in 1933 (39). In 1940, it was discovered that target oxidation affected secondary electron yields and sputtering rates. Throughout the 1950s and into the 1960s, optical thin film coatings were commonly applied to optical devices, including glass optics, lenses, and optical filters. The optical coatings acted to enhance optical performance and in certain applications to improve lifespans and robustness. Also at this time, new sputtering techniques became accessible such as CVD and molecular-beam epitaxy (MBE) that at the time allowed for high-quality thin films. The linear transport model, on which modern sputtering is based, was introduced in 1969. The model described when energetic particles collide with a solid surface, they bombard the surface, causing it to erode and eject surface atoms which deposit onto the substrate. Pulsed-DC was created due to a 1975 patent application. This patent application described a method of applying short, high-voltage pulses to a DC sputtering discharge to increase the sputtering yield and improve the uniformity of the deposited film. Early in the 1980s,

partial-pressure control was used to produce high-rate reactive sputtering. By controlling the partial pressure of the reactive gas, it is possible to control the rate of the chemical reactions that occur during the sputtering process, which can be used to create thin films with specific properties or at faster deposition rates. Eight Nobel Laureates in Physics and Chemistry contributed significantly to the development of modern sputter deposition.

Within modern electronics, thin films also played a key role, specifically in the fabrication of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) devices. The numerous thin layers of material needed to make MEMS devices and other electronic chips, were produced by layering thin films. Facilitating miniature electronics with high output performance. The fabrication of miniature electronics is only possible due to other thin film methods, such as wet/dry etching, photolithography, and mask alignment. The combination of all these methods allows for precise placement and exact patterning of a thin film in the range of nanometres.

In more recent times, the use of thin films has expanded to many more applications, still including optical coatings, but also to energy harvesting and production, biosensors, photovoltaic and ultrasonic devices. These films are also often used as protective coatings in the automotive and aviation industry, as well as to boost performance and lifespans.

In summary, thin films have played an important role for many years in a vast range of technologies and applications. The history of thin films has come a long way from the early beginnings as decorative coatings of 5000 years before the more recent advancements in technologies and broadening of applications, such as imaging systems, medical devices and gas sensing. Thin films have played a key role in the development of human technology and knowledge base.

Current technology

Thin film multilayer structures, are still used for decorative coatings today (40) and in more modern technologies such as semiconductor devices (41), overcoat protective coatings (42), photovoltaic cells (43), piezoelectric devices (44), integrated circuitry (45), data storage (46) and more (47).

Optical filtering (32) is a common application for thin film multilayer structures and is used to block bands of infrared radiation (IR) and better observe visible light, the captured spectrum more closely represents the visible spectrum of the human eye. Photography has optical filtration of visible light to achieve specific colour separation (48). Raman and fluorescence imaging are a key application where optical filtering is necessary (49). In general, optical filters act to selectively transmit wavelength bands of light and reject unwanted wavelengths for the desired application.

2.1.2 Thin film theory

The properties of thin films used in optical applications can be described by several models, including the optical properties model, the Drude model, and the free-electron model.

The optical description deals with the way in which light interacts with matter and thin film structures. In this model light is thought of as a wave and passes through thin films, the interactions are described in the transmission, reflection, and absorption of the material.

The Drude model describes the behavior of free electrons in a metal using classical physics. Proposed by Paul Drude in 1900, it assumes electrons are like a classical gas, interacting with ions via collisions. Electrons undergo mean free path trajectories between collisions, experiencing a relaxation time. The model simplifies quantum effects but captures electrical conductivity phenomena, describing macroscopic properties like resistivity. Despite its simplicity, the Drude model laid the foundation for understanding electrical conduction in metals and contributed to the development of more sophisticated quantum mechanical theories.

The free-electron model is a simplified theoretical framework is used to understand the behavior of electrons in metals. In this model, electrons are treated as non-interacting, free particles moving within a crystal lattice. The model assumes that electrons experience a periodic potential from the crystal lattice, leading to the formation of energy bands. The Pauli exclusion principle is considered to account for the filling of electron states. While the free-electron model neglects many real-world complexities, such as electron-electron interactions, it provides valuable insights into concepts like electrical conductivity, thermal conductivity, and the electronic struc-

ture of metals.

In addition to these models, there are also several factors that can influence the material properties of thin films, including the materials used, the host substrate, the thickness of the film, and the deposition method. To design and simulate thin film coatings for specific applications, all of these factors must be carefully taken into consideration.

2.2 Optical filters

Multilayer thin film optical filters are produced by alternating thin films with specific dielectric constants on top of a substrate or membrane. Light passing through the optic device will experience internal interference and wavelengths of light can be transmitted, absorbed or reflected from the filter. The properties of the filter design and wavelengths of interacting light will determine how the incident light interacts. Some common types of filters pass only high wavelength ranges (longpass), short wavelength ranges (shortpass) or a band of wavelengths (bandpass) which are blocked at high and low wavelengths.

2.2.1 Bandpass filter

A type of optical filter, known as a bandpass filter, allows only certain wavelengths of light to pass through and transmit while blocking the neighbouring wavelength bands. The width of the allowed-to-pass wavelengths is dependent on the filter design and the filter is traditionally named in the passing wavelength ranges or bands. This band of passing wavelengths can be narrowed to only let a small number of wavelengths through or widened

to allow pass of many more wavelengths of light. Where the bandpass begins to allow light to pass is referred to as the cut-on wavelength(s), this cut-on can cross a band of wavelengths and can be a gradual transmission or sharp with a single or few wavelengths. Similarly, wavelengths in which the light is rejected are called cut-off wavelength(s). These filters are also defined by the tuneable central wavelength and highest percentage transmission achieved.

2.2.2 Specific bandpass filtering - Fabry-Perot bandpass (FPBP) and wide band cut-off (WBCO) filters

A FPBP filter is a type of bandpass filter and is based on the principles of resonance. It consists of two mirrors that are separated by a small gap, known as the cavity, shown in Figures 2.1 and ???. When light is incident on the filter, it is reflected back and forth between the two mirrors, and the reflections interfere with each other, and then exit to the exit medium. This results in a series of peaks and troughs in the transmission spectrum of the filter, known as a Fabry-Perot interference pattern.

Figure 2.1: Example of a Fabry-Perot thin film optical transmittance filter

The two highly reflecting stacks, or mirrors, comprise alternating high, and

low refractive index materials and are separated with a varying thickness spacing layer (50). As the thickness of the spacer varies the central wavelength and bandwidth of the filter can be altered, this is shown in formula,

$$\lambda(x) = \frac{2n(x)d_{spacer}(x)}{m}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $\lambda(x)$ is the wavelength at a position, $n(x)$ is the effective refractive index at position, $d_{spacer}(x)$ is the thickness of the spacer layer at position and m is an integer representing the order of interference.

This type of bandpass filter has high transmission in the desired passbands but suffers from a limited wavelength range for out-of-band blocking. To extend the wavelength blocking range, a second filter is used, namely, a WBCO filter, to compensate for the poor out-of-band blocking and achieve the elimination of unwanted light passing, at a cost of minimally reducing the overall transmission of the resulting filter.

2.2.3 Linear Variable Filters (LVFs)

LVFs are specialised filters that are used to transmit a continuous range of wavelengths of light. These filters are called “linear variable” because they allow a continuous range of wavelengths to pass through them, rather than just a single wavelength or a discrete range of wavelengths. LVFs are commonly used in a variety of applications, including imaging, spectroscopy, and gas sensing.

Several factors must be considered when designing an LVF, including the range of wavelengths to be transmitted, the spectral resolution of the filter, and the size and shape of the filter. The range of wavelengths to

be transmitted is an important consideration, as it determines the overall performance of the filter. The spectral resolution of the filter refers to its ability to distinguish between different wavelengths of light, which is important for applications that require a high degree of spectral purity. The size and shape of the filter are also important considerations, as they determine the overall size and form factor of the filter.

LVFs are typically made of thin layers of material, such as dielectrics or a metallic films, that are deposited onto a transparent substrate, such as glass or plastic. The properties of the material used in the LVFs, as well as the thickness of the layer, can be carefully controlled to allow a specific range of wavelengths to pass through the filter. When designing an LVF optical filter, the choice of an appropriate full width half maximum (FWHM) is dependent on the specific application. If the FWHM is too wide, it can lead to a reduction in the resolution of wavelength. On the other hand, if it is too narrow, the detector might not collect enough energy, and there could be fabrication issues in achieving the desired filter design. Therefore, there needs to be a careful compromise in selecting the FWHM to ensure optimal performance for the intended purpose.

The spectral response of LVFs, often referred to as continuously variable filters or gradient filters, varies continuously, in a predetermined manner, along one dimension of the filter. Shifting the position of a linear variable filter by any amount will affect the filter's centred wavelength transmissivity. The gradient can change and is chosen for a specific use. In practice, LVFs allow instruments with several filters to be replaced with a single filter, streamlining designs and lowering the price of many measuring instrumentation. However, the fabrication process can be complex fabrication steps and non-uniformity in thickness may lead to distortions in the spectral response. Linear variable filters have applications with any

system requiring wavelength separation, this can include IR spectrometers (51), hyperspectral imager (52), medical imaging (53), gas analysis (54), material identification (55) and spectrometry (56). Within this study, the application is wavelength separation to achieve wavelength-separated images for HSI (57) and to allow spectral selectivity within non-dispersive infrared gas sensors.

2.3 Thin film growth mechanisms

Materials' inherent atomic structures and bonds give birth to a variety of material properties (58). These properties are taken into consideration while selecting for a particular application. Therefore, it is useful to know what material properties come from what atomic configurations, when working with thin films, as well as how the desired arrangements are produced.

2.3.1 Atomic arrangement and bonding

The arrangement of atoms within a material can be organised such as in a more crystalline structure or appear in a random order, otherwise known as an amorphous structure. Each of the atomic arrangements, and therefore structures, give different material properties. At the atomic level, structure differences can lead to differing mechanical, electrical and optical properties within a material. In the case of an LVF, deposited such that it has wavelength-dependant passbands along the length of the filter and as a result produces wavelength separation when visible light strikes the surface of the optic, and depending on the position along the filter, only light of a certain wavelength or colour can pass through, which is a result of optical thicknesses. The bonding of atoms within the material is what, in effect, gives rise to the material properties. Separate bonds affect the motion of light in separate ways, in three ways – through transmission, reflection and absorption (58; 59; 60). All of these are measurable properties and are used in defining thin films.

2.3.2 Nucleation and diffusion

Desirable atomic arrangement within a thin film can be accomplished in the initial growth stages during a deposition process. An approaching atom can either be reflected off of or adsorbed onto the surface of a substrate. If the substrate surface is not desirable, often a stepping intermediate layer, referred to as a bond or bonding layer, is used to promote thin film growth.

Thin film growth begins with nucleation in low energy processes, which is the term used to describe the location where an atomic structure forms during the early film growth stage. On a substrate, nucleation sites enable crystal formation and growth to occur. Two important factors which influence growth are substrate temperature – the barrier for nucleation to take place is larger with higher temperatures, and deposition rate – the barrier for nucleation to take place is smaller with a higher deposition rate (58; 59).

Film growth can happen by a number of mechanisms: Island growth known as Volmer-Web, Layer upon layer growth known as Frank-van der Merve, and an intermediate mechanism that possesses both 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional growth orientations known as Stranski-Krastanov. Figure 2.2 demonstrated the growth types as they form on a substrate.

From figure 2.2, for the Volmer-Web growth the material builds up into mounds to avoid interfacing with the substrate. This causes slower growth than the other two mechanisms and the material diffusion is lower. Growth by the Frank-van der Merve mechanism gives a smooth-forming film that encourages layered growth. Stranski-Krastanov growth starts as layer growth and develops into island growth after a few monolayers have grown (61).

Figure 2.2: Three common thin film growth mechanisms. (a) Volmer-Web (b) Frank-van der Merve (c) Stranski-Krastanov.

2.3.3 Kinetic theory of gases

The kinetic theory of gases is a straightforward, historically important classical model of the thermodynamic behaviour of gases that laid the foundation for many key thermodynamic notions. According to the model, gas is comprised of multiple identical particles (atoms or molecules) that are all moving rapidly and randomly. It is considered that they are substantially smaller in size than the particle spacing on average. Elastic collisions occur randomly between the particles and with the container's walls. The simplest form of the model only takes into account the interactions within the ideal gas. The theory relates and explains the relationship between volume, pressure and temperature, as well as viscosity, thermal conductivity and mass diffusivity.

2.3.4 Mean free path

In order to achieve thin film growth by PVD a low pressure (high vacuum - $10^{-3} - 10^{-7}$) setting is required. Within a low-pressure setting or environment, and as demonstrated by the Ideal Gas Law, there will be

a low number of particles contained within a given volume. The remaining particles can now travel further without collisions with one another. The particle density within the volume dictates the collision probability. In sputter deposition, this is critically important as the particles have to traverse long distances to reach substrates, relative to the diameter of the particles.

This average distance is known as the mean free path, λ , (59; 62; 63; 64), and is given by the relation,

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{2\eta\sigma}, \quad (2.2)$$

where the particle density is denoted by η and the collision cross-section of the gaseous particles within the system is denoted by σ .

In sputtering, the deposition chamber is the low pressure setting. This chamber volume is fixed, as such the pressure within the chamber is directly proportional to the number and density of molecules within the chamber at a fixed temperature. Equation 2.2, shows the inverse relationship between the mean free path and the particle density within the chamber, as the particle density decreases (i.e. a chamber pressure reduction) the mean free path increases. The longer mean free path then the lower the chance of collisions or particles within the chamber.

2.3.5 Molecular flow

As with increasing mean free path, the chance of particle collisions decreases, and the overall chamber behaviour changes. To describe these changes, flow regimes are used. Flow regimes are quantified by the dimen-

sionless Knudsen ratio or number, Kn , equation 2.3 relates the mean free path to the physical length of the chamber or volume, (59; 62; 63; 64).

$$\text{Kn} = \frac{l_c}{\lambda}, \quad (2.3)$$

where the physical length of the chamber or volume is denoted by l_c .

The Knudsen number calculated can be compared to the defined ranges below.

Molecular flow	Category
Free	$\text{Kn} \leq 1$
Intermediate	$1 \leq \text{Kn} \leq 110$
Viscous	$\text{Kn} \geq 110$

Table 2.1: Knudsen number ranges.

Free flow, $\text{Kn} \leq 1$, is the desirable molecular flow for growing thin films (65), there are many less collisions between particles within the fixed chamber volume and many more particles hold their initial velocities until impact with the substrate material.

2.3.6 Free Molecular Distribution

Probability distributions can be used to characterise gas molecules in the free molecular flow regime, when $\text{Kn} < 1$, and are helpful in identifying the state of a control volume. When doing these certain presumptions are made, such as that gas molecules in this regime move continuously and arbitrarily, only depending on the gas temperature. According to the ideal gas law approximation, “there are no interatomic forces between particles and kinetic energy is only transferred through elastic collisions, resulting

in a steady-state distribution of molecular velocities throughout the volume” (66; 67; 68). The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution function, $f(v)$, can be used to describe the gas particles after these presumptions have been established, as demonstrated in equation 2.4.

$$f(v) = \frac{1}{n} \frac{dn}{dv} = \frac{4}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(\frac{M}{2RT} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} v^2 e^{-\frac{Mv^2}{2RT}}, \quad (2.4)$$

where R is the ideal gas constant, T is the gas temperature, v is the gas molecule velocity, and M is the molar mass of the gas species.

Using the above distribution function, temperatures and gas species are all that are needed to define the gas-particle velocity. The kinetic energy of the system can be described by the gas’ temperature in the same way that the gas’ temperature represents the likely speed, (64). The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, which characterises the distribution of energy of the system, can be obtained from the well-known equation for kinetic energy indicated in equation 2.5,

$$K.E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2. \quad (2.5)$$

These patterns of distribution are what make it possible to gather crucial plasma parameters and explain the deposition process.

2.3.7 Particle flux

The particle flux describes the flow of particles to the substrate area when growing thin films and is used to determine the time in which the substrate

area will be fully coated. Particle flux is defined as,

$$\Gamma = n\sqrt{\frac{RT}{2\pi M}}, \quad (2.6)$$

where the ideal gas constant is denoted by R , gas temperature by T , particle flux by Γ , the mass of a gas molecule by M , and density of molecules by n .

2.3.8 Plasma

According to scientific literature (66; 69), a plasma is defined as an ionised gas. To comprehend the sputtering process and to measure plasma properties, it is crucial to understand how plasma interacts with a surface. One important factor to consider is the mass disparity between electrons and ions or neutral atoms; electrons are approximately five orders of magnitude lighter. Consequently, electrons move significantly faster than the other particles within the plasma, which causes any surface immersed in the plasma to become negatively charged rapidly, leading to a phenomenon is known as surface “floating” (64). This negative charge, in turn, draws ions towards the surface, leading to the formation of a quasi-neutral sheath between the bulk plasma and the negatively charged surface. Within this sheath, there is an unequal distribution of ions and electrons. When the ions have enough kinetic energy, which is determined by the negative bias of the surface, they can penetrate the surface and trigger a variety of events, including sputtering (66).

2.4 Sputter deposition

Thin films are a major focus within this project, specifically thin films produced by microwave plasma-assisted pulsed-DC magnetron sputtering. As the investigation details the fabrication and characterisation of linear variable filters.

2.4.1 Ion bombardment

A well-known PVD technique for thin film growth is the sputtering process. This process accelerates particles towards the target material with high energy and momentum. The energy should be enough to disassociate target material atoms from the surface and initial layers of the target. With ion bombardment onto a target surface, a number of factors influence what will happen. Factors that control sputter events are target material type, target surface, arrangement of atoms within the target, ion energy, ion species, and ion angle at collision.

Some sputter events that are influenced or controlled by these factors are not desirable or efficient for thin film growth. By taking into account the ions' kinetic energy and the momentum transfer between ions and target material atoms, the sputter yield can be maximised.

The sputter yield is optimised experimentally based on the above factors (59; 47; 70). To successfully sputter target atoms, the impacting ion's kinetic energy must be high enough to exceed the binding energy of the target material atoms. If the energy of the ions is too high, they will be implanted into the target material surface. If the ion energy is too low, the ion will most likely be reflected from the target surface as either a neutral

or ion. There is a range of energies where ions will transmit enough energy to eject target material. By aligning the mass and size of the incident ion and target atom, the momentum exchange between them can be optimised to boost sputter yield (59).

Another metric used to determine thin film growth and process evaluation is the rate of deposition. This is the rate of thickness change over a unit of time, typically measured in angstroms per second for sputter deposition. Using a known deposition rate, the total deposition time can be estimated for a final thin film thickness. Rates of deposition are material dependant and are measured experimentally with a set of deposition process parameters.

For this application a particular type of sputter deposition process is used, it is such that ions are accelerated using an electric potential close to the target surface, aimed at the target material. The electric potential is created by negatively biasing the target, this determines the ion kinetic energy and momentum that impacts the target. In practice, this would be applying a DC bias to the target to grow the thin films. There are other techniques used in the presence of a process gas during deposition, this is commonly referred to as reactive sputtering.

2.4.2 Reactive sputtering

Reactive sputtering is a deposition method that can be used to create thin films built from dielectric materials such as sulphides, nitrides, carbides, oxides, or a combination of these. The metallic target material that has been sputtered undergoes chemical modifications as a result of the introduction of process gas into the low-pressure environment. Depending on

the rate of deposition and the flux or flow of the process gas, this can lead to thin films with a range of stoichiometry. The thin film characteristics are also diverse because of the differential stoichiometry (59; 63). Pulsed DC sputtering is the approach employed in this study to achieve reactive sputtering.

2.4.3 Pulsed-DC sputtering

For reactive processes, pulsed DC sputtering is favourable. Time delay reverse biased pulses of DC current are sent to the sputter target, this delay time can be controlled for various target materials. During the reactive sputtering process, a target surface can form a layer of dielectric material through chemical reactions with the reactive gas. This build-up lowers the target purity and is known as poisoning the target. When these dielectric layers form, they float at a separate electrical potential from the target and create a capacitor-like effect between the conductive plasma and the conductive target. Positive charge buildup on the dielectric poisoned layer steadily increases until dielectric breakdown occurs resulting in electrical arcing.

With pulsed DC sputtering, the momentarily reversed bias periodically repels any positive charge build up on the poisoned dielectric surface, thereby minimizing arcing and maintaining a smooth steady deposition of material and offering a more effective deposition process. Due to the increased mobility of electrons as opposed to ions in the plasma, arcs can be diminished or eliminated by pulsing the target in the 10-350 kHz range with 50-90% duty cycles.

As the target surface alternates between positive and negative pulses, the

plasma's electrons rush to the target face to clear it of any charge buildup. This also generates heat, which acts to lessen and remove impurities. A secondary effect of pulsing the target is the enhancement of ionisation events, in turn increasing the ion density. This can help improve deposition rates and diffusion into the substrate.

2.4.4 Microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC magnetron sputtering

To enhance the quality of thin film coatings, microwave plasma can be utilised in the reactive sputtering process. This can be set up in a separate zone from the deposition zone. Separated deposition and plasma-enhanced oxidising areas allow for a metallic-like sputter deposition and then into a further oxidisation stage. This separation of zones generates thin films with much denser qualities and reduced pin holing (71). By only introducing reactive gas in the separated zone and inert gas at the depositing zones, the chance of target poisoning is greatly reduced (72).

2.4.5 Substrate Cleanliness

Within deposition technologies and thin film science, cleanliness is an extremely important factor to be considered. Within the industry the cleaning regimes differ from place to place, indicating there is no one fit all solution. One proven method to reduce contaminants such as organic material and produce higher quality thin films is the use of a microwave plasma etch prior to deposition (73). This is, however, a final step and comes after a series of substrate-cleaning steps. These steps may include ultrasonic cleaning, hand cleaning using solvents or detergents, baking the substrates

or polishing the surfaces.

2.5 Thin film optical design software

Thin film optical design software allows for the design, modelling and performance calculations of thin film optical coatings. Typically this includes reflectance and transmittance spectra, optical constant extraction and modelling capabilities for complex multilayer designs with user-input material files. The two used for LVF design and optical constant extraction are Essential Macleod and TFCalc software.

2.5.1 Essential Macleod

Essential Macleod is a thin film design software package that is useful for the design and performance calculation of optical coatings. It has the capability to calculate a wide range of performance parameters for various multi- and single-layer thin film coating designs, such as transmittance, reflectance and absorptance as functions of wavelength and angle. The software also has the capability to refine existing designs to improve their performance (74).

2.5.2 TFCalc

TFCalc is a thin film design software program which enables the analysis and design of multilayer thin film coatings. It has the ability to compute coating layer stacks of up to 500 layers with 150 separate materials and derive and modify the refractive index and extinction coefficient of modelled

thin film designs. The program has the capacity to examine how a change in parameter will affect coating performance (75).

2.6 Microwave plasma-assisted sputter deposition system

The MicroDyn system manufactured by Deposition Sciences, Inc. is a state-of-the-art deposition technology for the fabrication of high-quality optical coatings. This microwave plasma-assisted pulsed-DC reactive sputtering deposition technique is specifically designed to produce multilayer thin film optical coatings with high precision and accuracy, (71; 72; 52). The MicroDyn system is a versatile and powerful tool that has been utilised in a wide range of applications, including the production of LVFs. The details of the MicroDyn system, including its design, capabilities, and performance characteristics will be discussed.

2.6.1 Deposition system design and set-up

The system uses an electrically floating horizontal axis rotating drum, with the anode as the grounded chamber, and no external bias applied to the drum. This design allows for efficient and precise deposition of each layer of the optical coating. The deposition process is achieved by multiple passes across a rectangular planar magnetron source, as seen in figure 2.3.

The system uses a two-stage pumping regime to achieve a base vacuum of 8.5×10^{-6} Torr and has a unique design for efficient and precise deposition.

A base vacuum of 8.5×10^{-6} Torr is achieved by a two-stage pumping

Figure 2.3: (a) Exploded view of the microwave plasma-assisted reactive pulsed DC magnetron sputter coating tool used to fabricate high quality LVFs and (b) Front view schematic depicting separation of sputtered flux region and reactive plasma region [28]

regime. A rotary pump evacuates the system until a crossover point, 5×10^{-2} Torr, at which a turbomolecular pump takes the pressure down to the machine's base pressure.

2.6.2 Advantages and features of the MicroDyn system

Key advantages separate the MicroDyn from other sputter deposition systems, such as:

The metal-rich sputtered film in the microwave plasma zone can be readily oxidised. The drum rotation speed is chosen so that two monolayers are

deposited over the magnetron targets each cycle. This pulsed-DC reactive sputtering system's microwave plasma features separate sputtering and oxidation zones, which is a key feature. Only argon gas is used at the target region, whereas reactive gases are used at the microwave plasma zone. By delivering metal-like sputtering and segregated microwave-plasma-assisted oxidation, permits quick deposition rates and high-quality films with fewer pinholes due to suppression of energy.

Microwave plasma enhancement occurs when molecular oxygen species are broken down into atomic oxygen species, increasing reactivity and allowing for more uniform and effective oxidation of growing oxide layers. A high-wattage 20 kW DC power source is used in the MicroDyn system, resulting in an energetic process with enhanced film packing density. This is also true for less reactive processes such as nitrides.

Pulsed-DC has the advantage of decreasing arcing and thus increasing film uniformity by reducing the quantity of solid material ejected from the target face and incorporated into the film as a result of hard arcing.

Quartz crystal oscillator thickness monitoring is in use within the Microdyn. The quartz crystal oscillator method for thickness monitoring employs an oscillating piezoelectric slab of quartz where the period of oscillation reduces as the thickness of the material put on it increases. The rate of thin film deposition is monitored, in real-time, and the process is terminated once the correct layer thickness has been achieved.

The MicroDyn employs a Meissner trap to freeze water vapour and other condensable substances onto a cold cryocoil surface in order to catch them. Water vapour within the chamber, which is notoriously difficult to eradicate with a turbomolecular pump alone due to the adhesion to chamber walls, is greatly reduced. Warm water can be circulated around the system jacket,

when the system is at atmospheric pressure with the door open, or in the initial pumping down of the system. This acts to evaporate any water from the inside walls and reduce the chance of water getting into the chamber.

The use of a partial pressure controller allows for complete control over the partial pressure of oxygen. As a result, because oxygen reactivity fluctuates throughout the process, uniform oxidation of the film can be obtained.

An Inficon IC/5 closed-loop process controller is used to regulate the thickness of the films deposited in the MicroDyn. The device determines the frequency shift for an oscillating piezoelectric quartz crystal head owing to increasing mass and acoustic impedance shift during deposition and monitors and controls the rate and thickness of thin film deposition. An uncoated crystal oscillates at a frequency of 6 MHz, while a “fully” coated crystal oscillates at a frequency of 4.5 MHz. The thickness precision is approximately 0.5%, however, it is subject to process variables such as sensor placement, thin film stress and temperature.

There are four vacuum gauges in various positions within the chamber, which display reading on the front panel of the system, summarised in the table 2.2:

Process temperature is monitored by thermocouples inside the chamber. The thermocouples are situated in front of the target, between the target and the sample. Heat-sensitive stickers are placed on the substrates to measure the local temperature of the substrate which is then used to calibrate the thermocouple (as thermocouples are 50 mm from the substrate surface). The same sputter process was used to calibrate the system and ensure further thermocouple measurements represented actual temperature during the deposition process. Throughout the deposition, the temperature is sampled, and the maximum temperature experienced during sputter

Gauge	Location	Function	Range
Pirani	Vacuum chamber	Monitor roughing pressures	1×10^{-3} Torr
Convection Convection Convection	Backing line	Monitor backing pump pressure	Atmosphere to 1×10^{-4} Torr
Hot cathode ion	Vacuum chamber	high vacuum	1×10^{-3} to 1×10^{-10} Torr
Baratron capacitance manometer	Vacuum chamber	Absolute pressure readings during process	extremely low pressures

Table 2.2: Vacuum gauges installed on the microwave plasma assisted deposition system.

deposition was 70°C (heating was directly a result of material deposition).

2.7 Cleaning techniques

An ultrasonic cleaning line was used for substrate cleaning prior to loading for deposition. Substrates are translated through four heated baths, each step has a specific role in the cleaning process. Baths one and two are a 3% potassium hydroxide solution and detergent, respectively, for contaminant and grease removal. Bath 3 is a hot water station to remove any remaining solutions from previous baths. Bath 4 is a slow drain water-only bath designed to remove water from cleaned substrates using the surface tension of the water to drag water from the surfaces, resulting in a completely clean, dry substrate.

2.8 Metrology and characterisation methods

The Aquila nkd-8000 (Aquila Instruments Ltd., Blackburn, UK) allows for the simultaneous measurement of optical transmittance and reflectance of thin film samples from 380 nm - 1700 nm, allowing for analysis in the visible and near-infrared. The system utilises a 100 W quartz tungsten halogen lamp and spectra can be captured using s-, p-, or non-polarised light with a spectral resolution of 1 nm and a spot size at the sample of 5 mm. Spectra can be measured over a continuously variable angle from 10 - 90° For semi-absorbing films the system has typical repeatability of 0.01%.

The Perkin Elmer 983 spectrophotometer is a laboratory-grade double-beam IR spectrometer that the independent measurement of optical transmittance and reflectance of thin film samples from 2000nm - 20000nm, allowing for analysis in the infrared. Perkin Elmer is considered the standard for the optical coating industry.

The E+H Metrology GmbH (model MX- 203-6-33) Wafer geometry gauge measures the coating stress prior to any deposition processes, also a post-deposition measurement is made. By comparing the pre and post-measurements using a capacitive distance sensor and 32 points on the wafer surface, the system calculates the thin film stress on a substrate using the Stoney formula (76) with the associated error.

2.9 Conclusion

To conclude, optical filters are essential in several industries for numerous applications, ranging from telecommunications, gas sensing, and imaging

systems. Understanding the mechanisms by which thin films grow, can help in the design and fabrication stages of high-performance optical filters with specialised optical properties. Due to the high performance required for the filters, the technique is a popular deposition choice due to precise thickness control and high-quality films that can be produced. Moreover, the use of thin film optical design software can significantly aid in the design and optimisation of optical filters. The 4000 series MicroDyn deposition system provides highly advanced capabilities for the sputter deposition process, making it a unique and valuable asset in thin film filter fabrication. Proper cleaning techniques are essential to ensure the high quality and performance of the fabricated filters. Finally, the metrology and characterisation methods used to evaluate the optical properties and performance of optical filters are critical to ensuring their effectiveness.

Chapter 3

Design, fabrication and characterisation of linear variable filters

3.1 Introduction

The investigation details the design, deposition and performance of deposited LVFs for use within a HSI camera and a miniaturised multi-gas sensor, as a linearly variable wavelength separation method.

3.2 Substrate cleaning

3.2.1 Substrate cleaning and plasma etch

Before all depositions, substrates follow a cleaning procedure to improve film adhesion and reduce sample contaminants, to improve the thin film

optical performance, thus improving overall quality. All substrates are cleaned using an ultrasonic cleaning line and loaded into the deposition chamber.

3.2.2 Plasma pre-clean etch

Substrates then undergo a microwave argon plasma pre-clean treatment inside the vacuum chamber at low pressure. This consists of an argon plasma clean to rid the surface of any organic material or residual water (77). The microwave power used is 3 kW and the argon flow is 100 sccm at the substrate surface for 600 seconds. The argon plasma acts to rid the substrates of any contaminants that will be vaporised from the substrate surface (77). Microwave pre-cleaning raises the substrate temperature and primes both the system and the substrates for deposition.

Whilst the plasma pre-clean is a measure to also clean the system and remove unwanted water or contaminants, there should also be maintenance cleaning of the vacuum system to ensure each thin film deposited is free of contaminants and less likely to cause pin holing, this offers an enhanced thin film quality. A build-up of thin film debris on chamber walls or metalwork will lead to flaking material and these flakes can land on substrate surfaces causing issues with film adhesion and optical absorption.

3.3 Single layer deposition and analysis

3.3.1 Optical constant extraction

Essential Macleod optical material modelling software was used to derive the optical constants (refractive index n and extinction coefficient k) of the single-layer thin film coating materials, which are necessary to model the optical performance of a multilayer thin film optical interference filter design (74). The following sections include a description of the single-layer material optical model in detail. The multilayer thin film interference coatings that make up the LVFs fabricated in this study were designed and modelled using the single layer coating material optical constants obtained from the Essential Macleod fitting software (74). From the envelope fitting method, each material was fit to a 3-term Cauchy model and the refractive index and extinction coefficient values derived.

3.3.2 LVF static masking for linear thickness gradient coating

In this study, MathCAD-15 was used to model and optimise an LVF sputtering mask. To obtain a linear thickness uniformity across a substrate. A program was written to design deposition masks and calculate the desired thickness distributions for a configuration of substrates on a rotating drum, considering deposition geometry such as a target and a mask with

pre-defined shape function,

$$Thickness(X_s) = \sum_{\theta} \sum_{X_t, Y_t, Z_t} \frac{\cos(\beta - \beta_0)^n \times Trackfield \times \cos(\gamma)}{r^2}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\cos(\beta - \beta_0)$ is the angular distribution function, (β_0) is the angle of maximum emission, and n is a power modified distribution and is related to the target material; it can be determined through measurement and fitting (57). By relating the magnetic field to the erosion track profile, a 2D data array is obtained as *Trackfield*, $\cos(\gamma)$ corrects for the drum and substrate rotation (γ being the angle between the beam/substrate and normal incidence), and r is the drum radius.

Thus, using functions with a desired thickness distribution for the LVFs, a mask geometry was designed. Previous static uniformity masks have been designed for the system in a similar manner (78). The LVF mask was modelled on Creo 3D CAD software and manufactured using computer numerical control (CNC) machining.

The mask shape is such that, precise linear coating thickness distribution is achieved along the length of the filter, and uniform thickness across the traverse direction. The resulting thin film is produced with a predetermined thickness gradient allowing for a wedge-shaped optical coating (57). The wedge separates the wavelengths of light permitted to pass through while blocking other neighbouring wavelengths (57). The deposition system sputter target, mask design and position, substrate and resulting wedge-shaped coating are shown in figures 3.1 and 3.2.

Figure 3.1: (a) Static masking arrangement used to tailor linear coating thickness gradient and (b) 3D schematic of the multilayer wedge-shaped optical interference coating (LVF).

Figure 3.2: Picture of static masking arrangement used to tailor linear coating thickness gradient

3.3.3 Single layer deposition and optical constant extraction

On fused silica glass, a single layer of thin film Nb₂O₅ was deposited using the static LVF masking arrangement, deposition parameters are shown below in table 3.1. The optical transmittance (%) and reflectance (%) spectra were analysed using an Aquila NKD8000 spectrophotometer (79) in the visible spectral band and data fit using Essential Macleod software

to extract the optical constants, n and k.

Parameter	Nb_2O_5	SiO_2	Ge
p.p. O2 (Torr)	9.8×10^{-4}	8.0×10^{-4}	0
p.p. Ar (Torr)	4.0×10^{-3}	4.0×10^{-3}	4.0×10^{-3}
Rate (Å/s)	1.4	0.4	1.1
Microwave power (kW)	3	3	0
Regulation	Current*	Voltage*	Voltage*
Ramp time (s)	15	2	15
Voltage (V)	340	420*	410
Current (A)	9.25*	5.5	6.5
Power(kW)	3	2.3	2.5
Ar flow (sccm-1)	190	190	190
O2 flow (sccm-1)	120	32	0

Table 3.1: Nb_2O_5 , SiO_2 and Ge deposition parameters.

The Essential Macleod software package was used to fit the measured transmittance (%) versus wavelength spectral fringes. The software uses the envelope method, (74), after the user defines the half-wave optical thickness (HWOT) and quarter-wave optical thickness (QWOT) points. This extracts the optical constant values defined at the HWOT and QWOT points. These discrete values are then fit to a 3-term Cauchy model, (80), giving smooth interpolated curves for the optical constants of the deposited thin film materials.

The same optical model was used to fit a top layer of SiO_2 that was deposited over the Nb_2O_5 layer to create a double layer. The optical transmittance of single-layer materials is depicted in Figures 3.3 and 3.4.

Figures 3.5 and 3.6 present the estimated refractive indices and extinction coefficients for thin films of Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 . The visible LVF was modelled using this optical constant data.

Figure 3.3: Measured single layer Nb_2O_5 optical transmittance on JGS3.

Figure 3.4: Measured double layer SiO_2 on Nb_2O_5 optical transmittance on JGS3.

Figure 3.5: Derived optical constants using Essential Macleod optical constant extraction for Nb₂O₅.

Figure 3.6: Derived optical constants using Essential Macleod optical constant extraction for SiO₂.

3.4 Linear variable filter modelling

The single layer extracted optical constants for Nb_2O_5 and SiO_2 are used in an Essential Macleod design software to model a visible LVF. The LVF design is a combination of two optical interference filters, each filter is deposited on either face of a glass substrate, shown in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Design of an LVF with separate coatings on either side of a glass substrate and incident and emergent media of air.

The first optical filter is a 3-cavity FPBP filter, which is a narrow bandpass filter. This design has alternating high and low index materials, at a desired central wavelength for the filter and produces a steep bandpass shape for limited wavelength passing.

A common limiting factor for LVF designing is unwanted sidebands which are observed at either end of the spectral range – this is a limiting factor for LVF spectral range, as a narrow passband is needed for the spectral selection of a single wavelength of light over the full range of operation – the range is limited by any light admission out with the stop bands.

To counteract this limitation and extend the operational wavelength range, a WBCO filter is added. The WBCO filter is deposited on the opposite face of the substrate, this is a wide bandpass filter and is used as an out-

of-band blocking method, centred at the same reference wavelength as the FPBP filter, with a much wider passband.

The stopbands extend beyond the upper and lower spectral range of the LVF to ensure adequate out-of-band blocking of the unwanted sidebands when the FPBP filter is centred at the extrema of the LVF operational range. The FPBP filter and WBCO filter design spectral transmittance curves are represented in figures 3.8 and 3.10.

The bandpass spectral curve can be calculated for various positions along the physical length of the optic by giving the LVF a desired physical length and scaling all layer thicknesses by a group factor. The spectral bandpass shape for various points along the LVFs' physical length is presented in Figure 3.9 and 3.11.

The main factors affecting the LVF spectral shape are the FPBP filter bandwidth and the LVF coating thickness (and therefore spectral) gradient.

Visible LVF

The 3-cavity FPBP has design sub/(HL)² 4H (LH)⁵ L 4H (LH)⁵ L 4H (LH)², where H and L stand for high index (Nb₂O₅) and low index (SiO₂) materials, respectively, at an optical thickness layer of one-quarter wavelength with a reference wavelength of 570 nm. The FPBP filter design requires 33 layers in order to achieve the desired spectral blocking and narrow wavelength passband. The WBCO filter design requires 115 layers in order to achieve the desired out-of-band blocking range at total coating thicknesses of 8.7 μm. The length of the LVF is intended to be 40 mm.

The FWHM was calculated to be 11.25 nm. LVF characterisation was conducted using a spectrophotometer (Aquila nkd 8000) equipped with an optical fiber to produce a narrow spot size (1 mm); the filter was characterised on a motion stage.

Figure 3.8: Designs for Fabry-Perot and wide-band cut-off optical interference filters with reference to the central position and wavelength transmittance spectral curves for a visible LVF.

Figure 3.9: A model of the visible LVF optic's transmittance spectrum was created using several tooling factors to reflect the different physical optical interference filter film thicknesses.

Mid-IR LVF

The MID-IR LVF design follows similar steps as the visible LVF preparation:

- Single-layer depositions of Nb_2O_5 and Ge using parameters in table 3.1
- Single layer measurement using a Perkin Elmer 983 spectrophotometer
- Optical constant extraction and analysis
- Design of mid-IR LVF optical filter and modelling at various positions

The 3-cavity FPBP has design sub/(HL)² 4H (LH)⁵ L 4H (LH)⁵ L 4H (LH)², where H and L stand for high index (Ge) and low index (Nb_2O_5) materials,

respectively, at an optical thickness layer of one-quarter wavelength with a reference wavelength of 3750 nm.

Figure 3.10: Designs for Fabry-Perot and wide-band cut-off optical interference filters with reference to the central position and wavelength transmittance spectral curves for a mid-IR LVF.

The FWHM was calculated to be 182 nm. LVF characterisation was conducted using a spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer 983) equipped with a narrow spot size (1 mm); the filter was characterised on a movable stage. The FPBP filter design requires 33 layers in order to achieve the desired spectral blocking and narrow wavelength passband. The WBCO filter design requires 143 layers in order to achieve the desired out-of-band blocking range at total coating thicknesses of 15.3 μm . The length of the LVF is intended to be 6 mm.

Figure 3.11: A model of the mid-IR LVF optic's transmittance spectrum was created using several tooling factors to reflect the different physical optical interference filter film thicknesses.

3.5 Structure test

For single-layer deposition and optical constant extraction, an estimated deposition thickness and rate are entered into the IC/5 deposition controller based on prior publications (72; 81; 35). These estimates are material dependant and have to be used in quartz crystal calibration for accurate aggregated thickness control and deposition rates. The deposition rate changes over target usage and will not equal the input estimated thickness. Due to this, a correction factor is used within the Essential Macleod model to relate the estimated thickness to the measured thickness through the optical fitting of the deposited thin film.

The correction factor calculation is then multiplied by any desired single

or multilayer thicknesses for a material and will account for the estimated deposition thickness and the measured deposition thickness. A correction factor larger than one, if the deposited coating is thickness is less than estimated and less than one if the deposited coating's thickness is more than estimated.

Both Nb₂O₅ and SiO₂ materials had an estimated input thickness of 1000 nm. Fitting the deposited single-layer samples gives a thickness of 1090 nm and 992 nm, for SiO₂ and Nb₂O₅, respectively. The correction factor, calculation for each layer is detailed in equations 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4 :

$$Correction\ factor = \frac{\text{input thickness}}{\text{fitted thickness}} \quad (3.2)$$

$$Correction\ factor = \frac{1000}{1090} = 0.92 \quad (3.3)$$

$$Correction\ factor = \frac{1000}{992} = 1.01 \quad (3.4)$$

For each material, the correction factors are multiplied by the desired thickness and programmed into the IC/5, equation 3.5 shows this.

$$IC/5\ thickness = \text{desired thickness} \times \frac{\text{input thickness}}{\text{fitted thickness}} \quad (3.5)$$

In order to assess the validity of the single-layer film thickness estimated from optical fitting (therefore the correction factors and optical constants), a test structure was deposited.

Comparing the experimentally deposited thickness achieved with the mod-

elled thicknesses gives the overall error and can then be calculated and used for further correction.

The design programme is then used to enter the experimental data as design targets. The TFCalc software was used for this. Deposited layers of the same material are given a group (Group 1 is all SiO_2 layers and Group 2 is Nb_2O_5 layers).

The group factor for each group is a quantity that multiplies the thickness of the layer in the original design to produce a design with different layer thicknesses. For the original design, the group factor for both materials is 1. The software's optimisation function is then used to optimise each of the groups to fit the design to the experimental data, producing a new group factor for every material used.

3.6 Microwave plasma-assisted reactive pulsed DC magnetron sputter deposited linear variable filters

The modelled multilayer optical interference LVBs were deposited using high and low refractive index materials - amorphous niobium pentoxide (Nb_2O_5) and silicon dioxide (SiO_2), and Germanium (Ge) respectively. Sputtering from a 99.95% pure niobium target, a 99.999% pure silicon target and a 99.999% pure Ge target (supplier Testbourne Ltd, UK) was used to deposit necessary oxides using a microwave plasma-assisted reactive pulsed DC magnetron sputtering technique and using the mechanical masking setup shown in earlier sections.

An Aquila NKD8000 spectrophotometer (79) and a Perkin Elmer 983 Infrared Spectrophotometer (82) are used to investigate the thin film coatings and to evaluate the optical transmittance as a function of wavelength.

3.6.1 Measuring deposited LVF performance

The successfully deposited LVFs optical transmittance (%) are evaluated as a function of wavelength to gauge deposited performance against modelled performance.

Figure 3.12 and 3.15 display the observed optical transmittance as a function of wavelength at various positions along the coated optic's physical length as solid lines, while the model is shown as dotted lines for both visible and mid-IR LVFs respectively.

The differences between the simulated and experimental curves are caused by the finite spectrometer beam spot size utilised to measure the samples of 1 mm, which causes measured curve broadening and damping because of the coating thickness gradient (57). As can be seen, the filter design provides good out-of-band blocking across the whole wavelength range, and the centre wavelength of the bandpass curve is linearly translated.

From Figures 3.13 and 3.16, the measured central wavelength corresponds to the modelled filter. Moreover, there is an agreement between the linear centre wavelength along the length of the deposited LVF. A gradient of 10.83 nm/mm is calculated from the measured visible LVF result and 346.67nm/mm for the Mid-IR result.

VIS LVF performance

Figure 3.12: Spanning the length of the LVF, optical transmittance was measured at various x -coordinates. Above each measured passband, the x -coordinate position is displayed in millimetres. Modelled spectra are represented by dot lines, while solid lines represent measured spectra.

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Figure 3.13: Measured centre wavelength for the manufactured LVF as a function of x -coordinate position. In accordance with the LVF's design values of 10.83 nm/mm, linear fitting shows obtained linearities of 0.999 and linear dispersion coefficients.

Figure 3.14: Fabricated LVF picture showing distinctive colour separations along the length of the filter with thickness gradient.

Mid-IR LVF performance

Figure 3.15: A model of a Mid-IR LVF optic's transmittance spectrum was created using several tooling factors to reflect the different physical optical interference filter film thicknesses.

3.7 Conclusion

In this chapter, a theoretical model of the LVFs is presented, based on optical constant extraction from microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC magnetron sputtered single layers. Optical constants extraction was achieved using the Essential Macleod software envelope and cauchy fit method of the single layer on glass transmission curves and presented. Using Essential Macleod software and the extracted single-layer optical constants, a theoretical model was constructed to model the behaviour of the LVFs, comprising of a substrate, a WBCO filter and a FPBP filter. The WBCO filter consisted of alternating layers on one side of the glass substrate and the FPBP consisted of 33 layers on the opposite face of the substrate. This gives the desired selective passbands of visible and mid-IR light with

Figure 3.16: Measured centre wavelength for the manufactured LVF as a function of x -coordinate position. In accordance with the LVF's design values of 346 nm/mm, linear fitting shows obtained linearities of 0.998 and linear dispersion coefficients

out-of-band blocking required at each extreme of the chosen ranges. A structured test was carried out to better understand and confirm the deposition rates of the multilayer structure. Microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC magnetron sputtered deposition of the full LVF was carried out successfully and the LVF optics are characterised using an Aquila NKD8000 spectrophotometer and a Perkin Elmer 983 Infrared Spectrophotometer. Results of the deposited LVF were in excellent agreement with the modelled design, shortfalls with transmission peaks were due to the limited spot size and spectral averaging over the narrow wavelength passband and its neighbouring blocking wavelength bands. The fabricated LVF achieved good agreement with the modelled filter design with measured linearity of central wavelengths above 0.99 over the filter's active range. The designed

3.7. CONCLUSION

and deposited LVFs are suitable for wavelength separation needed for HSI and use within a HSI camera and for use in a miniaturised multi-gas sensor.

Chapter 4

Prototype Hyperspectral Imaging camera

4.1 Introduction

This chapter begins with an introduction to hyperspectral imaging and its application is given. The assembly and testing of a prototype hyperspectral imaging camera are presented, along with the comparison to a commercially available high-end system. The chapter finishes with the prototype camera testing out in the field and the results of algorithm development.

4.2 Agricultural monitoring

Agricultural monitoring refers to the use of various techniques and technologies to provide detailed information about crop, pest, disease, and irrigation management. The data is collected and analysed to boost overall agriculture output by using predictability and control measures. Thus, im-

proving farming efficiency while reducing the potential risks of unforeseen crop losses due to disease spread, inadequate pest control and mistiming of harvests. Manual methods of monitoring such as soil probing, or large field inspections are labour or time intensive and are prone to errors. The accumulation of data can also be performed by drones, satellites, and sensors. The gathered data from agriculture monitoring sensors can be temperature, air quality and soil moisture. Imaging or videoing whole fields or large crop patches using drones or satellites can give insights into crop quality, soil richness and estimates of total yields. The data gathered is also highly reliable and far less prone to mistakes or human errors. To predict any potential issues, vast amounts of data collected from crops and processes are analysed for signs of potential problems or issues. Farmers and agricultural specialists can make informed decisions about the condition of crops and increase optimisation and yields for harvest. This is of particular interest and importance in recent times for crop productivity, food security and deep space exploration on long-haul missions. As it is essential to know which areas of the plant need attention, to limit disease spread, monitor plant growth, and stop drought. These are all essential for crop cultivation and harvesting.

These issues have been addressed by non-destructive HSI technologies (57; 83; 84; 85; 86; 87; 88).

4.3 Overview of a hyperspectral imaging camera

A HSI camera is a type of device that captures images across many spectral bands or wavelength bands in the electromagnetic spectrum. This allows

the system to capture images of an object or scene and generate many wavelength bands for each pixel. The traditional camera can only record images in three wavelength bands (red, green and blue) within the visible spectrum. Limiting the spectral resolution and missing the detailed spectral information contained in each image taken. The spectrum produced in HSI imaging for each pixel over all the wavelength bands creates a unique “spectral fingerprint”. HSI imaging can be thought of as traditional imaging directly followed by spectroscopy to extract deeper information from matter using the reflectance spectrum. Information within fingerprints is used in many applications, such as material identification, counterfeiting analysis, chemical detection, disease detection, and waste recycling. HSI cameras are used in many fields that require detailed analysis such as geology, agriculture, military, and environmental monitoring. Moreover, they are versatile in operation, often mounted to drones and UAVs or used as static devices and observing objects passing below mounted on a conveyor belt or similar.

4.3.1 Wavelength separation methods

The ability to capture images or videos and extract spectral information and interrogate to distinguish between unknown materials or to identify disease or signs of ill health is extremely valuable. To gain spectral information from hyperspectral images, wavelength separation is needed. There are several ways to do this when capturing images, such as diffraction gratings (89), prisms (90), and LVFs (90). A common HSI wavelength separation technique is a diffraction grating. A diffraction grating consists of an optic which has parallel slices of material removed in various angles to create a diffraction pattern when light is passed through (91).

4.3. OVERVIEW OF A HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGING CAMERA

This method is commercially available and is used within HSI cameras and other spectrophotometers as they can produce high accuracy and spectral resolution. Diffraction gratings suffer alignment issues, and temperature sensitivity and are expensive to produce. A second wavelength separation optic used in HSI is prisms. The prism technique separates light into its constituent parts based on the principle of refraction (92). The prism is an angled transparent optic that has well-polished surfaces to allow different wavelengths of light to refract differently. This method is used in laboratory spectrometers and has a high spectral resolution. However, have limitations such as sensitivity to alignment, bulkiness, and a limited spectral range. LVFs are a relatively new technique for HSI as a wavelength separation method (93). LVFs produces a linear thickness gradient along one axis of the optic which permits different wavelengths along the length of the filter while maintaining a uniform thickness in the transverse direction. LVFs offer many advantages over traditional wavelength separation techniques, including high throughput, low cost, compact size, and low sensitivity to temperature and alignment changes (57). LVFs are also capable of separating light over a broad spectral range and can be easily integrated into HSI cameras and spectrometers. Due to the advantages over traditional wavelength separation methods, LVFs are increasingly being used within HSI systems as an alternative solution with applications in agriculture, such as by *Liaghat et al. (2019)* (83), LVFs were used to detect basal stem rot (BSR), a fatal fungal disease of palm oil plantations, and assess the health of palm leaf samples (87). Moreover, LVFs are used for environmental monitoring to detect disruptive algal blooms in water bodies (94). Also within medical imaging, LVF-based HSI cameras are employed to detect skin cancers and other harmful skin conditions (53).

HSI using LVFs as the wavelength separating method have significant ad-

4.3. OVERVIEW OF A HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGING CAMERA

vantages over common wavelength separating techniques. The design and modelling are complex to achieve due to the optical filter specifications. Moreover, the deposition of LVFs requires high precision thickness and precise process control. However, with the use of static masking (95), and the advantages offered by the 4000 series MicroDyn Deposition system as employed to produce desired LVFs for use within a low-cost hyper-spectral imaging system as the separation method.

4.4 Hyperspectral imaging system assembly

Hyperspectral imaging requires the capture of high-quality wavelength-separated images. These images have to be wavelength specific and captured in a short timeframe to preserve the imaging conditions and to ensure minimal movement of the subject.

In order to achieve wavelength-separated images, an LVF with a linear variation of spectral transmission along an axis can be translated across a sensor. Therefore, with multiple images taken in quick succession along the length of an LVF, the images captured are of different wavelength ranges. The images then require processing. The processing involves high-level algorithms to sort the captured images into full images of specific wavelengths or hyperspectral images.

4.4.1 Hardware Structure

To achieve the quick and clear capturing of wavelength-separated images using an LVF, it is crucial to have an indexing mechanism that can scan the LVF across the sensor smoothly and accurately.

This is because any vibration or instability in the scanning mechanism can result in blurring or distortion in the captured images, which can affect the accuracy of the post-processing and analysis.

The indexing mechanism selected was a custom rack and pinion method, controlled by a stepper motor. The LVF is then stepped by the high-spatial-resolution monochromatic image sensor (1.3MP IDS E2V CMOS Image Sensor) and the sensor is allowed to capture images at each step before moving to the next.

4.4. HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGING SYSTEM ASSEMBLY

The 40 mm LVF is attached to an LVF holder that was specially developed and 3D printed. A rack and pinion system was used to connect the holder to a high-resolution step motor, and the gearing ratio was chosen in order to enhance the resolution of linear movement, where one step from the motor corresponded to 0.1 mm of linear movement. The linear variable filter scans across the imaging sensor in steps, this takes an image at each step, which creates wavelength separated strips, these strips are then recombined and stitched together into entirely wavelength separated images.

Figures 4.1 and 4.2 provide a summary of the mechanical arrangement of the HSI components.

Figure 4.1: Schematic of LVF manipulation via rack and pinion method.

The system above can scan across the LVF at a relatively high speed, covering the full length of the LVF in around 20 seconds for a full high-resolution spectral scan achieving a spectral resolution of 4.5 nm, table 4.1 gives details required to manipulate the LVF. Multi-spectral and lower spectral resolution images will take considerably less time than this. The position of the LVF is controlled using an Infrared optical sensor and the LVF is returned to a known home position before each image scan, the LVF position is both accurate and repeatable.

Stepper Motor Profile	Units	Comments
No. Gear Teeth	21	
Pitch of Rack	0.942478 mm	PI*MOD
Module (MOD)	0.3	
PCD	6.3 mm	
Degree/step	1.8 mm	
Degrees/tooth	18 mm	
Total Required travel	40 mm	
Required travel/step (min)	0.1 mm	
Minimum distance/step	0.09896 mm	
Number steps/rev	200	

Table 4.1: Profile of the step motor with rack and pinion set up

To ensure that the imaging system is as versatile as possible, a 50 mm C-mount lens is included, pictured in Figure 4.3, the lens is directly in front of the sensor and with the LVF translating between. This allows the device to have any number of lens types attached to the standard C-mount system depending on the application.

4.4.2 **Fabricated visible linear variable filter**

As discussed in Chapter 3, the results of the deposited LVF were found to be in excellent agreement with the modeled design, indicating that the designed and deposited LVFs are suitable for wavelength separation needed for hyperspectral imaging and use within an HSI camera. However, the

Figure 4.2: 3D CAD drawing of LVF manipulation, including home sensor function

shortfalls with transmission peaks were observed due to the limited spot size and spectral averaging over the narrow wavelength passband and its neighbouring blocking wavelength bands. Nonetheless, the fabricated LVF achieved good agreement with the modeled filter design with measured linearity of central wavelengths above 0.99 linearity over the filter's active range. The camera aperture is set at $4 \mu\text{m}$ to accommodate the sensor size, aiming to mitigate the averaging effect induced.

4.4.3 Final hyperspectral imaging camera

The HSI camera developed has an LVF integrated in front of the image sensor that translates through the spectral profile of the LVF at high speed to capture wavelength-separated images. A home sensor has been fitted to reset the LVF filter before any images are acquired, ensuring accurate wavelength separation and repeatability. The camera is equipped with a C-mount lens to allow image capture at a variety of distances and illumination

4.4. *HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGING SYSTEM ASSEMBLY*

scenarios. The final camera developed allows for rapid and precise HSI in the visible range.

Figure 4.3: Final HSI camera build with internals exposed.

4.5 Image acquisition, correction and calibration

4.5.1 Image acquisition

A graphical user interface (GUI) was developed with the University of Strathclyde Hyperspectral Imaging Centre (96) to control the imaging system that allows the user to capture images of any wavelength in 1 nm increments (57). The software can be used to capture a specific range i.e. 450-475 nm, or an entire range of 450-850 nm within 30 seconds. The scene is viewed in real-time on the right-hand side of the test utility as shown in Figure 4.4 - in this instance, a standard Macbeth chart was used as a scene, this is similar to “live view” on digital cameras.

Figure 4.4: HSI camera GUI developed with accompanying software.

4.5.2 Correction

Once the hyperspectral datacubes were captured and reordered, several correction steps were undertaken. Both a ‘Gretag-Macbeth’ colour chart and a Spectralon calibration tile were imaged in the scene along with the plants/leaves of interest. This allowed for the negation of varying illumination effects (sun moving behind clouds outdoors *etc*).

4.5.3 Wavelength calibration

The device was calibrated using standard gas discharge lamps, set-up shown in figure 4.5. Hydrogen and helium were chosen as both have a number of emission lines in the visible spectrum, as detailed in the table 4.2.

Helium lines (nm)	Hydrogen lines (nm)
492	486
501	656
505	
587	
667	
707	

Table 4.2: Emission lines for He and H.

Figure 4.5: Hydrogen discharge lamp set-up

A high-resolution scan was used to image the lamps over the complete wavelength range of 450 nm to 850 nm. The actual step position that each of the above discharge lines displayed in the calibration photos was compared to the expected step position (thus the LVF position). The wavelength’s

4.5. IMAGE ACQUISITION, CORRECTION AND CALIBRATION

theoretical step position was then brought into alignment with the actual step location by adjusting the scan's starting point. The device's information was compared to the LVF's wavelength data after being calibrated. Table 4.3 and figure 4.6 show how the LVF wavelength varies along the length of the filter, where 0 mm is the centre point of the LVF.

LVF position (mm)	Measured Wavelength (nm)
-18	469
-12	535
-6	605
0	675
+6	743
+12	809
+18	875

Table 4.3: Measurements of LVF wavelength varying along the length of the deposited filter

Figure 4.6: LVF wavelength varying along the length of the deposited filter.

Figure 4.7 is a typical calibration plot after the adjustment has been made. Once calibrated, the H and He lines of emission closely match the expected step position, with a discrepancy between the predicted and actual wave-

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length of no more than 3 nm.

Figure 4.7: calibration plot after the adjustment of LVF placement.

4.6 Spectral/spatial processing and dimensionality reduction

4.6.1 Spectral/spatial processing

Spectral/spatial processing and dimensionality reduction are important steps in the analysis of hyperspectral data. These steps can help to improve the accuracy and efficiency of the analysis by reducing the complexity of the data and eliminating redundant information.

4.6.2 Data cube

The camera captures 3-dimensional hyperspectral datacubes by translating an LVF across the field of view, creating discrete vertical strips at linearly spaced wavelengths in each image. This results in different wavelengths being spread across a single frame and the spatial data for an individual wavelength is dispersed across many consecutive frames. These images, taken at subsequent steps in time, are then re-ordered to form the datacube in the traditional arrangement where there are two spatial x and y dimensions, as with traditional image capture systems. The z dimension represents the wavelength (λ). The term “spatio-spectral imaging” refers to this technique for collecting hyperspectral data, due to the capture of varying spatial and spectral data spread across the sensor and can be seen visually below in Figure 4.8

Figure 4.8: An image depicting the spatio-spectral method of capturing a hyperspectral image datacube in ordered steps.

4.6.3 Extraction of Regions of interest

In order to extract meaningful spectra (*i.e.* the plants/leaves and not the background) regions of interest, or ROIs, had to be determined. This was carried out by visual inspection of the images. Once these ROIs had been determined, only the relevant spectra were extracted from the image and saved. It is at this stage that the class labels are assigned to this extracted data.

4.6.4 Standard Normal Variate Normalisation

standard normal variate (SNV) is a common tool in hyperspectral data pre-processing (97; 98) to correct for scatter and noise effects. Each spectrum is normalised by subtracting its mean value followed by division by the spectrum's standard deviation. This process creates an average of zero and a variance of one for every spectrum in the set. The formula for SNV can

be seen in Equation 4.1 and the effect of applying SNV in Figure 4.9

$$I_{\text{corr}} = \frac{(I_{\text{orig}} - (\overline{i_{\text{orig}}}))}{(\sigma_i)} \quad (4.1)$$

Where, I_{corr} is the SNV corrected image, I_{orig} is the original image, $\overline{i_{\text{orig}}}$ is the mean sample spectrum and σ_i is the sample spectrum standard deviation.

Figure 4.9: The SNV process and impact on a series of wavelength captured pixels.

SNV is employed to reduce the effects of illumination differences or noise by removing the mean bias. Like-pixels with comparable spectra should be categorised similarly with a normalised intensity regardless of variations in original illumination levels.

4.6.5 Principal Component Analysis

principal component analysis (PCA) is a common statistical procedure that seeks to decorrelate a set of highly correlated high-dimensional data using orthogonal basis-vectors (99). PCA is often quoted as being the optimal compression technique but is not widely used as each of the orthogonal

basis vectors must be calculated on an image-dependent basis making it not well suited for practical image compression. It is however, a commonly used method of dimensionality reduction as each basis-vector is the eigenvector pertaining to the sorted eigenvalues of the data, meaning that each subsequent basis vector conveys less and less information. Using this, we can retain the first k -components where $k \ll L$, where L is the total number of wavelengths in the data. By keeping only k components it is possible to discard redundant information in the interest of decreasing the computational overhead associated with high-dimensionality data. With this, however, comes a cost as by retaining only k coefficients, there is a loss of information however as the objective is classification rather than compression and reconstruction, this is not of concern. There are multiple methods of setting k , one of which is to look at the amount of information each coefficient conveys and select it manually or by selecting an ‘elbow’ point. Another method, and the one utilised for the hyperspectral imaging system, is to simply retain a percentage variance or percentage of information (100). The PCA dimensionality reduction procedure was conducted out using a Python Package for PCA (101). An example of PCA-based dimensionality reduction from 2 dimensions to 1 is shown below in Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10: Stages of PCA on 2-Dimensional data.

4.7 Data elaboration and development of prediction and classification models

4.7.1 Random sampling and training/testing data extraction

With the data captured, corrected, normalised and its dimensionality reduced, the classification process can begin. First, a subset of all captured spectra is selected to form the training set required to train an SVM whilst the rest can be used for validation and testing at later stages.

4.7.2 Support vector machine training

SVM-based classification is binary and aims to draw a hyperplane (a line in 2-D) between two classes. For multiple classes, One-Vs-All binary classification is carried out. As there are an infinite number of hyperplanes that can separate some classes of data, the training process of an SVM seeks to maximise the margin between two sets of clusters of data. The case of a 2-D decision space is shown in Figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11: SVM training with maximum margin between cluster sets.

In order to train the model, a number of representative examples must be shown to the model during the training stage. The training seeks to find an optimal solution which it reaches recursively.

The model is subjected to different cases or classes at the ROI selection stage, the model then tries to iteratively find the best answer. Once trained, the SVM can categorise and predict unseen images into the classes defined in the training stages. An SVM classifier was used in the development of the algorithm for data analysis and classification of crop types and crop

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diseases.

4.8 Comparison to a high-end hyperspectral imaging system

The HSI camera was originally designed as a low-cost hyperspectral imaging system, and as part of that process, it was benchmarked against a high-end push-broom hyperspectral imaging system. The cost of the hyperspectral imaging system was approximately a tenth of the push-broom benchmark device.

Figure 4.12: A labsphere reflectance standard (left) was utilised to characterize the HSI camera (middle) and push-broom system (right) and compared against the reference spectrum.

The sample and a white card were imaged using both the low cost camera and the high-end push-broom system. The acquired spectra were initially normalised against the white card and subsequently against the high end push broom system. Resulting in the normalised spectra presented in Figure 4.12. This multi-step normalisation ensures comparable spectral data between the low-cost camera and the high-end push-broom system.

Both the designed system's and the conventional push-broom HSI system's acquired spectra have significant correlations and closely mirror the manufacturer's reference spectrum graph in the 450-850 nm range, shown in figure 4.12. Both systems' spatial and spectral resolutions were evaluated for equivalent parameter values. Low-cost Hyperspectral imaging system with a step size of 4 and pushbroom binning of 4. The results are shown

in the table 4.4.

Device	Spectral Resolution (nm)	Spatial Resolution (Pixel number)
HSI Camera	4.53	1280 x 1024
Pushbroom system	2.44	377 x 366

Table 4.4: Comparison table for the spectral and spatial resolutions of a high-end system against the HSI imager with similar setup settings.

Though the spatial resolution of the hyperspectral imaging system far exceeds that of the push-broom system, the spectral resolution of the push-broom system is approximately double the performance, when using comparable settings. Despite the reduced spectral resolution, the spectral data acquired by the hyperspectral imaging system is accurate when compared to the reference reflectance standard and demonstrated accurate data classification.

4.9 Field testing

4.9.1 Classify all spectra using the SVM

With a model trained using the training data, the SVM attempts to classify unseen testing data. This test data is placed in the same space as that in which the SVM was trained and based on where it lies in the decision surface it can be grouped into one of the classes.

The hyperspectral imaging system was successfully trained for crop classification. The images show the identification of crops entirely on spectra (lettuce, rocket, spinach), which was first done on leaves in good condition (control samples). The camera proved to be able to discriminate between healthy potato leaves (green) and unhealthy potato leaves (red) using this

technique after it had been further refined and applied to both healthy and unhealthy crops. The discrimination between several varieties of salad leaves and the identification of late blight in potato crops were both accomplished using the SVM-based classification of the acquired data.

Spectral imaging was carried out by placing the instrument on a tripod and capturing a calibration image using a ‘Macbeth’ colour card before each vegetation image capture. Sensitivity was adjusted by visually examining the number of overexposed pixels in the image “live view”, to achieve an appropriate colour and exposure balance under the highly variable lighting conditions (rapidly moving clouds). Leaves from the potato plants were removed from the plants and taped to a white background on a post, which was then imaged using the camera. The spectral correction was carried out using the colour card image post-capture.

Classification of salad leaves

For each salad leaf type, spinach, rocket and lettuce, ROIs were extracted and split into both training and testing data sets. The training set was used to make prediction equations using the SVM classifier. The accuracy of the SVM classifier was examined using the test set. PCA was used for dimensionality reduction and feature extraction. The SVM utilized the Radial Basis Function Kernel and determined the optimal parameters through grid search using k -fold cross-validation. The SVM classifier results are presented in Table 4.5 and Figure 4.13.

With the exception of some evident uncertainty between spinach and rocket, the SVM recognises the various salad leaf varieties accurately. This highlights the separability of the data clusters and the effectiveness of the SVM-based model, which averages over 94% accuracy on all never-seen-before

Figure 4.13: Classification of spinach, rocket and lettuce leaves

Class	Training image Accuracy (%)	Unseen image 1 Accuracy (%)	Unseen image 2 Accuracy (%)
Lettuce	99.99	99.97	100.00
Rocket	99.64	99.43	96.54
Spinach	99.27	92.59	78.12

Table 4.5: Classification of salad leaves results

photos.

Classification of healthy and unhealthy crops

In order to classify late blight, healthy and infected leaves from the “Orchestra” potatoes variety were imaged from Plots 6 and 20. For imaging these leaves were collated and fixed to a black card, the black card removes the unwanted background and creates a favourable imaging environment. The same pre and post-data analysis steps were carried out as before after

image capture. A portion of the data was used as a training set and the remaining data as a validation test set, the data chosen for each set were randomly sampled. Training data consisted of 10% of the data from two leaves of each class, shown in Figure 4.14, to train the SVM before it was used to classify any new images. The healthy and infected leaves from Plot 6 were used to train the SVM to categorise between regions of blight and no-blight, this was tested using a mix of leaves. The resulting classification from leaves in Plot 6 samples are shown in Figure 4.14, where the leaves that are highlighted green are healthy and red are diseased. The resulting classification of the healthy and infected leaves is largely accurate; however, if a majority voting process were adopted, each leaf would be categorised totally as healthy or unhealthy depending on the dominant class.

From plot 6 most of the leave area displayed signs of either health or infection. Plant leaves taken from Plot 20, a separate “Orchestra” cultivar, had local areas of blight on the leaves. Smaller ROI areas were selected that showed clear signs of blight and no blight, these regions served as the training data. The model was retrained using the new classes and an SVM was trained which was validated using the test data set. Figure 4.15 displays the results of classification. The resulting model had an accuracy of 88% in discriminating between healthy and unhealthy pixels.

Since several of the scanned plants were not exhibiting symptoms at the time of imaging, this level of accuracy is promising. This degree of accuracy suggests that the HSI camera can be used to detect agricultural pathogen infection at an early stage, enabling time for treatment and preventing crop production loss (57).

Figure 4.14: Classification of crop health into two classes.

4.10 Conclusion

In conclusion, LVFs were deposited with a novel microwave plasma assisted sputter deposition process which utilises a custom static mask design in order to achieve correct thickness gradient along the length of the filter for use within a HSI camera. The system was calibrated against emission lines from helium and hydrogen lamps and showed excellent agreement with no measurement found to be greater than 3 nm. A feature algorithm was developed which effectively distinguished between similar leaf varieties and obtained approximately 88% accuracy in distinguishing healthy and late-

Figure 4.15: Classification of healthy and unhealthy where only small regions display signs of blight.

blight-expressing classes of potato plant leaves using SVM classification. The final camera assembly delivers a performance compatible with that of a high-end HSI system. This offers a high price-to-performance ratio at around 1/10th of the cost.

Chapter 5

Thermopile detector enhancement

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, a thermopile enhancement investigation is carried out with a focus on improving the output voltage in the presence of IR radiation by introducing a broadband absorber coating directly onto the thermopile photosensitive area.

5.1.1 Thermopile detector overview

IR sensors can be categorised into two main types: thermal and photonic. A thermopile is a type of IR detector used to detect thermal fluctuations. They are often favoured over photonic detectors due to their ability to last for long periods of time without drifting, cost-effectiveness, and ease of use. They also offer a wide spectral response for a variety of applications, including non-contact thermometry, thermal flow sensors, non-dispersive

infrared (NDIR) gas sensors for CO₂, and thermal imagers (102).

A thermopile chip typically follows a structure, shown in Figure 5.1, comprising of a base substrate (conventionally silicon due to its low cost and compatibility with CMOS wafer processing (103)), a membrane isolation layer (known as a membrane layer), a series of connected thermocouples (thermopile), and an IR absorbing thin film for improving the IR absorption. The “hot” junction is designed to be thermally separated from the “cold” junction and suspended in the membrane to improve the temperature differential between the two junctions. To generate a measurable output many thermocouples are connected in series together, this increases the weak signal to a measurable level.

Figure 5.1: Typical thermopile crosssection with key constituents labelled.

In the presence of IR radiation, the absorbing thin film heats generating a temperature difference, ΔT , between the hot and cold junction of the thermopile, this is converted into an electrical output by the Seebeck effect (104). The electrical output is heavily influenced by the absorptance of the

incident IR radiation by the thermopile.

An industry standard technique to enhance the broadband absorptance of the IR absorbing layer is to apply a highly porous metal, known as “metal black”, to the detector’s photosensitive area. These coatings usually consist of gold-black, silver-black, or platinum-black (105; 106; 107). A major drawback of these coatings is the complexity involved in the coating process, high associated costs, damage-prone and ill compatibility with CMOS wafer processing. Furthermore, next-stage processing can become more complicated using metal black coatings as the devices become more brittle and susceptible to damage (105).

As an alternative to the metal black coatings, a sandwich layer can be used, such as a $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multilayer structure. However, this can have issues due to narrow absorption profiles and low overall IR absorption (105; 108; 109; 110).

To address the inadequacies of the metal-black and $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multilayer techniques, this investigation presents a new durable broadband Absorber (BBA) multilayer optical coating that is CMOS compatible and is based on a two-layer structure of hydrogenated carbon.

5.2 Thermopile detector theory

The thermal gradient produced by the incident IR light between the hot and cold junctions is converted to an electrical signal by the number of thermocouples connected in series. This thermoelectric signal is directly linked to the number of thermocouples, the Seebeck effect and the efficiency

of the absorbing thin film layer. The relationship can be defined by,

$$V_{\text{output}} = N\Delta T|\alpha_A - \alpha_B| = N\Delta T\alpha_{AB}, \quad (5.1)$$

where the number of thermocouples is denoted by N , materials A and B Seebeck coefficients are denoted by α_A, α_B . Between the hot and cold junctions the temperature distribution can be expressed as,

$$\Delta T = \frac{\eta P_o}{G_{\text{th}}}, \quad (5.2)$$

where the material absorptance is denoted by η and the detector's total thermal conductivity is denoted by G_{th} and P_o is the incident power. Substituting Equation 5.2 into Equation 5.1, provides,

$$V_{\text{output}} = N\frac{\eta P_o}{G_{\text{th}}}|\alpha_A - \alpha_B| = N\frac{\eta P_o}{G_{\text{th}}}\alpha_{AB}, \quad (5.3)$$

describing the output voltage as being directly proportional to the absorptance of the thermopile, η . Therefore, optimising the thermopile absorptance efficiency over a specific wavelength range will have a direct effect on the output voltage and final performance of the thermopile sensor.

5.3 Broadband absorber modelling

The design consists of a two-layer structure of hydrogenated and non-hydrogenated carbon and was modelled and thickness, thus absorptance of the thin film structure, on top of the base membrane structure was optimised using Essential Macleod optical coating design software (106).

The base membrane structure comprises of an $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multilayer, shown in Table 5.1. Modelling the structure produces an average absorptance value across the 2.5–20 μm spectral region of $(42 \pm 1)\%$, presented by the solid line in Figure 5.2. The base membrane results in a specific detectivity (D^*) value of $1.0 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}\sqrt{\text{Hz}}\text{W}^{-1}$ (111).

Layer Material	Physical Thickness (nm)
Si_3N_4	600
SiO_2	450
Si_3N_4	170
SiO_2	570
Si_3N_4	110

Table 5.1: Membrane structure detailed with materials and thicknesses .

Figure 5.2: Membrane and BBA overcoat modelled using Essential Macleod.

In an earlier publication, the influence of hydrogen on durable infrared optical coatings deposited via pulsed DC-sputtering has been examined (112). Single layers based on the layers previously investigated were deposited and examined using the Essential Macleod software envelope fitting method, the optical constant extraction and interpolation, described in Chapter 3. The extracted optical constant data was input into the software and used to

create an optical coating design model to optimise the desired absorptance at various thin film thicknesses to maximise the absorptance with a bulk carbon layer and a top anti-reflection (AR) layer to minimise reflected radiation. The result of the optimisation is shown as the dotted line in figure 5.2.

The optimised thicknesses for the carbon bi-layer, termed the BBA multilayer optical coating, is given in Table 5.2 and Figure 5.3.

Layer Material	Physical Thickness (nm)
Hydrogenated carbon (AR layer)	636
Nonhydrogenated carbon (Absorber layer)	2000
Si ₃ N ₄	600
SiO ₂	450
Si ₃ N ₄	170
SiO ₂	570
Si ₃ N ₄	110

Table 5.2: Membrane structure with carbon BBA overcoat detailed with materials and thicknesses.

Figure 5.3: BBA structure schematic.

By comparing the bare membrane structure and the membrane structure topped with the BBA multilayer optical coating in Figure 5.2, there is clear broadband absorptance enhancement over the desired spectral range. The optimal result of the optimisation of absorptance using carbon layers is a factor of over 2.2, from the membrane coating averaging 43% and the

membrane with BBA overcoat achieving 94%.

5.4 Broadband absorber deposition and measurement

The deposition of the BBA multilayer optical coating was carried out by the 4000 series MicroDyn deposition system using a pulsed-DC magnetron sputtering technique. Hydrogen is introduced during the deposition in a uniform and controlled manner by a high-purity hydrogen generator (Linde/NMH, model - 500) using the electrolysis of water (112; 113). The typical deposition parameters are presented in Table 5.3. A range of absorber layer hydrogenation levels was investigated for stress alleviation on 6-inch silicon thermopile device wafers and the thin film stress characterised by an E + H metrology GmbH (model MX- 203-6-33). Varying hydrogenated samples also underwent an optical transmittance and reflectance investigation, this was measured using Perkin Elmer 983 G infrared spectrophotometer. The film's absorptance was calculated from the optical transmittance and reflectance.

Ar Flow	H2 Flow	Power	Current	Voltage	Pulsed DC Frequency	Pulse Length
(sccm)	(sccm)	(kW)	(A)	(V)	(kHz)	(μ s)
100	0 to 5	4	10	400	66	4

Table 5.3: Typical deposition parameters for pulsed-DC deposited carbon thin films with the absorber layer ranging from 0-5sccm flowrates during deposition.

5.5 Broadband absorber testing and results

The deposited BBA multilayer optical coatings onto 6-inch silicon device wafers were investigated for optical performance and thin film stress as well as the final device performance testing at the device level.

5.5.1 Optical performance

The optical performance of the deposited varying hydrogen level BBA multilayer optical coatings is presented in Figure 5.4. From the average results of absorptance across the desired spectrum, 2.5-20 μm , the non-hydrogenated sample provided the optimal overall absorption and $94 \pm 1\%$.

With increasing hydrogenation within the absorber layer of the deposited films, a trend is observed with increasing transmittance, thus reducing absorptance. This trend is due to hydrogen incorporation into the sputter-deposited carbon significantly decreasing the infrared optical absorptance due to a decrease in deep absorptive states associated with dangling bonds (112; 114; 115).

Figure 5.5 demonstrates the average absorptance versus the hydrogen level. The best-performing absorptance hydrogenation level is 0 sccm or no hydrogenation. and with increasing hydrogen content the absorptance severely drops, at 5 sccm to a value of 33%. This supports the modelling that no hydrogenation at the absorber layer offers the highest overall absorptance, therefore device performance due to the contrast between the hot and cold junctions.

Assessing the modelled and measured performance shows good agreement and high overlap in Figure 5.6. The average modelled and measured results

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Figure 5.4: Absorbance for BBA multilayer optical coatings with varying hydrogen flows in the bulk absorber layer from 0-5 sccm.

Figure 5.5: Average absorbance for BBA multilayer optical coatings with varying hydrogen flows in the bulk absorber layer from 0-5 sccm.

post-deposition both achieve over 94% across the 2.5-20 μm region.

Figure 5.6: Modelled and measured BBA coating with the membrane structure for comparison.

5.5.2 BBA coating stress performance

The average and central stress on the 6-inch silicon device wafers was also investigated for the flow range 0-5 sccm in the absorber layers of the BBA coating. The difference in measurement results for pre and post-wafer deformation and the wafer bow can be used to gain information using the Stoney formula on the thin film stress within the coating (76).

The resulting thicknesses, crosssection measured by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and example measurement for 2 sccm flow absorber layer shown in Figure 5.7, and associated stresses are provided in Table 5.4.

All measurements obtained from the stress evaluation using the wafer stress gauge show the coating is in compression, meaning the coating is causing the wafer edges to bow away from the centre of the coating. The results of the compressive stress with varying hydrogen flow are graphed in Figure 5.8. The peak stress measured was 429 MPa with an absorber hydrogen

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Hydrogen Flow Absorber Layer (sccm)	Physical Thickness Measured by SEM (μm)	AVG Stress (MPa)	CNT Stress (MPa)
0	2.81	275	241
1	2.55	378	349
2	2.63	429	346
3	2.91	363	304
5	3.20	204	185

Table 5.4: Thickness and stress results for varying hydrogen levels within the bulk layer of the BBA coating.

Figure 5.7: SEM image cross-section of the BBA coating with the bulk absorber layer and the top AR layer labelled.

flow of 2 sccms. Conversely, the lowest stress value was measured at 5 sccm. A gradually increasing trend is observed from 0 sccm flow up to the peak stress value, after which the stress falls to the lowest value. Low-stress values are desirable for the thermopile overcoat thin film to minimise the number of device breakages on a 6-inch wafer.

Figure 5.8: BBA multilayer coatings deposited with varying hydrogen flows in the bulk absorber layer and associated compressive stress results.

5.5.3 Absorptance/stress relationship and Optimisation

The information gained from the optical and stress evaluations with varying hydrogenation levels is used for optimising the best overall performing BBA optical coating with respect to minimal device breaks but maintaining high absorption to maximise the hot and cold junctions thermal distribution, in turn boosting the thermopile performance.

Considering both the stress and optical performance of the varying hydrogen level absorber layers, shown in Figure 5.9, the non-hydrogenated absorber layer provides the best trade-off between high absorption of thermal radiation with a lower end compressive stress value. This is suited to the thermopile fabrication process and design goals of achieving a much-boosted performance with relatively neutral stress.

Figure 5.9: Varying hydrogen absorbance as a function of stress for use in the absorber layer.

5.5.4 Optimised coated thermopile chip testing

Uncoated thermopiles and thermopiles with the BBA multilayer optical coating were subject to output voltage testing. Thermopiles were tested from all sites on the wafer, the sites were North, East, South, West, and Centre, as shown in Figure 5.10.

Figure 5.10: Tested sites on a 6-inch silicon device wafer.

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A known blackbody source (Yangzhou Tuanrui Electric Co., Ltd/High-temperature ceramic heating plate) was used that has emission in the 2.5 to 20 μm region illuminated each thermopile at equal distance and the thermopiles voltage output measured by a probing system, pictured in Figure 5.11. The system steps through the thermopiles and records the output voltages measured, this is in line with standard industry practice for thermopile testing.

Figure 5.11: Industry experimental setup of voltage output testing of the device wafers.

The output voltage results, in Table 5.5, from the uncoated and coated thermopiles at each site ranged from 196- 254% boost and an average of all

5.5. BROADBAND ABSORBER TESTING AND RESULTS

Site	Voltage output with BBA - V_a (mV)	Voltage output without BBA without BBA - V_n (mV)	Percentage boost (%)	Average percentage boost (%)
Centre	392	197	199	220
East	330	168	196	
North	372	185	201	
South	261	104	251	
West	285	112	255	

Table 5.5: Device wafer testing under a broadband Infrared source at each site for Coated and Uncoated thermopile chips.

thermopiles tested produced a 220% enhancement with the BBA multilayer optical coating. The average enhancement of the output voltages agrees with the modelled estimates. The performance of the thermopile after the BBA overcoat gave a D^* value of $1.9 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}\sqrt{\text{Hz}}\text{W}^{-1}$ (116).

Calculation	Membrane structure	Membrane structure with BBA
Standard Deviation	18.03	20.7
Average percentage Standard Deviation (%)	12	6

Table 5.6: Correlation between coated and uncoated thermopiles.

The measured voltage output results show a clear correlation between the uncoated and BBA coated thermopiles. The optimised carbon absorber systematically enhances the voltage output across all 5 wafer sites. The large variation in enhancement per site is due to the initial irregularity in the uncoated thermopiles, prior to any BBA overcoat. As demonstrated in Tables 5.5 and 5.6, the average voltage variation and percentage standard deviation between non-absorber and absorber-coated thermopiles have a spread of 12% and 6% respectively. This suggests the BBA not only boosts the overall voltage output produced but also acts as a stabiliser for the thermopiles and narrows the spread across the wafer sites of the output

voltages.

5.6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the aim of the investigation was to improve the output voltages of thermopile IR detectors. The aim was achieved by designing, modelling, and depositing a BBA multilayer optical coating onto thermopile devices. The BBA multilayer comprises a bilayer of nonhydrogenated and hydrogenated carbon from a bulk absorber layer and a top AR layer. The enhancing BBA multilayer boosted the broadband absorptance within the 2.5-20 μm range and minimised the reflected IR radiation. The modelled bilayer boosted the thermopile performance by a factor of 2.2, enhancing the device's performance. Separate stress and absorptance investigations resulted in an optimised BBA thin film, where the bulk layer was a nonhydrogenated layer. The optimised coatings' boost was confirmed by testing the deposited bilayer on thermopile devices against control samples with no overcoat. Thermopiles with the coating performed 220% better than counterparts with no coating and a narrowing of the output voltage spread was observed. The primary concern is ensuring that the voltage output of the thermopile as high as possible, as it is directly related to the ability of the thermopile to convert thermal energy into electrical energy for enhanced sensitivity of detections. This type of thermopile could be used in gas detection systems for gas analysis as the sensing element. The boosted performance offers a more sensitive thermopile to IR radiation. This is of particular interest in NDIR CO_2 gas sensors.

Chapter 6

Carbon Dioxide Gas sensor

6.1 Introduction

This Chapter introduces NDIR gas sensing principles and the detection of CO₂ using different types of emitters and detectors. A comparison is then made between an in-house built sensor and a gas sensor available from industry. The performances of both sensors are evaluated and conclusions are drawn on which is most appropriate for the space-based CO₂ environment plant study.

6.1.1 History

CO₂ sensing has been a major topic in the gas-sensing industry for many decades (117). It is essential for various applications such as air quality monitoring (118), the detection of CO₂ in industrial environments (119), and as part of scientific research for monitoring CO₂ within our atmosphere (120).

Early CO₂ gas sensing was predominantly done with electrochemical sensors, which use chemical reactions to measure the concentrations of gases in an environment (121). Specifically, reactions between CO₂ molecules in the immediate environment with an electrolyte solution produce a measurable current that can be converted to CO₂ concentration. While these sensors were cost-effective, they were limited by accuracy and had short lifespans. Also, electrochemical sensors are prone to poisoning by other gases (122).

New optical gas sensing technologies became available throughout the 1970s and 1980s, such as NDIR gas sensors. Optical NDIR gas sensors allowed for much more accurate and repeatable measurement of CO₂ concentration due to the sensors operating principle (123). NDIR gas sensing involves the measurement of IR absorption by CO₂ molecules (124). Typically, an infrared source, such as an LED or micro hotplate, irradiates a chamber which is full of the target gas, the gas acts to absorb a proportion of the light and a detector, such as a photodiode or a thermopile, detects the remaining infrared radiation (125). The measurement is compared with the reference channel outside the CO₂ absorption, to determine the CO₂ concentration within the gas cell or gas chamber (125).

With time there were many improvements to the light source and detector within NDIR gas sensing. High-power infrared light sources were developed in the 1990s (126), followed by optical filtering which allowed for a more selective and stable CO₂ measurement. The advancements in microelectronics on signal processing allowed faster processing times and more sophisticated real-time analysis, thus further improving NDIR CO₂ gas sensing accuracy.

From the 2000s, NDIR CO₂ gas sensors moved towards LEDs primarily as the light source. Traditional IR light sources were larger, less reliable, and

had a shorter life span than the available LEDs at the time. LEDs are also suited to portable lightweight CO₂ gas sensors (127). Moreover, the miniaturisation of low-power electronics, allowed for a cost-effective lightweight battery-operated NDIR CO₂ sensor, which has become commonplace in public and industrial settings.

In more recent years, NDIR CO₂ sensors have become more sophisticated with the advancement of micro technologies, such as MEMS and the internet of things (IoT) (128). These micro technologies and advancements improved data processing speeds and enabled the integration of multiple sensors to a singular device, making real-time CO₂ measurement and control possible from remote locations (129).

There have been many advancements throughout the history of CO₂ and NDIR gas sensing. From the early years of electrochemical sensors to the current state-of-the-art photoacoustic NDIR gas sensing, the field has come a long way,

6.1.2 Electromagnetic radiation and the mid-IR region

The electromagnetic radiation (EM) spectrum, which includes all infrared light, is a continuous range of frequencies or wavelengths, from the longest wavelength radio waves to the shortest wavelength gamma rays. The spectrum can be subdivided based on wavelength and defined by the type of EM radiation emitted.

The longest wavelength part of the EM spectrum are radio waves, these waves are typically used for communication, navigation and broadcasting. Next is microwaves which find a use for communication but have applica-

tions and sensing the environment and cooking food. The next division with a shorter wavelength is infrared radiation, and this is produced by all objects emitting thermal energy. Within the infrared radiation division, there are three subdivisions. these are the near-infrared (NIR), medium-infrared (MIR), and far-infrared (FIR). The typical ranges associated with each IR region can be defined as NIR from 0.75-1.4 μm , MIR from 1.4- 14 μm and FIR from 14-20 μm . The IR region is followed by visible light, ultraviolet, X-rays and finally gamma rays, all with progressively shortening wavelengths.

The characteristic absorption bands of multiple important molecules and gases are located in the MIR region of the EM spectrum. Often termed the “fingerprint” region, shown in figure 6.1 this makes it an area of significance for optical gas sensing (130). This region also has distinct windows, including wavelength ranges 3-5 μm and 8-12 μm , that are free from water absorption, making them ideal gas detection zones.

Figure 6.1: Mid-IR region of the EM spectrum with various gas absorption bands present.

The molecules of each gas species have specific rotational-vibrational transitions, which contain information on gas species and gas concentrations (131). Based on this, gas identification and quantification are possible. The vibrational modes of a gas species molecule relate to the ways in which

atoms vibrate relative to each other. The CO_2 molecule consists of two hydrogen atoms bonded to one oxygen atom covalently. When incident IR at a specific wavelength is incident on the molecule, it is absorbed, and the bonds excite causing them to vibrate. The CO_2 absorption band is shown in Figure 6.2. The associated absorption band of the molecule is centred around the vibrational transition wavelength. The band generally has a width of 2% around the major absorption wavelength, this is caused by the rotational transitions of the molecule that happen spontaneously.

Figure 6.2: Mid-IR region of the EM spectrum with CO_2 gas absorption bands present only.

6.1.3 Gas detection methods

There are many techniques for the detection of gas species and concentrations, these techniques can be broadly characterised into two main categories: interactive and non-interactive.

Among the interactive method is chemical and electrochemical sensors. Chemical detectors work by reacting the target gas with chemical substances, the interaction changes the chemical or physical properties of the substances in proportion to the gas concentration. Electrochemical, on the other hand, detect the change in the electrical signal by reacting the target gas with sensing materials. The change in the ability of the material to resist or conduct gives details about the gas concentration.

The non-interactive method relies on spectroscopic techniques, such as optical IR sensors. The sensor measures the concentration by detecting the amount of absorbed IR radiation by the target gas. The absorbed radiation is directly proportional to the gas concentration.

The selection of the appropriate method is dependent on the application. Each modality has associated advantages and disadvantages. Interactive chemical and electrochemical sensors are generally low-cost and offer a relatively quick response, however, are limited in sensitivity and long-term stability, and are sensitive to temperature or humidity. In contrast, non-interactive optical IR sensors operate with a higher accuracy, sensitivity, selectivity, and stability.

When selecting a sensor for a specific application, several factors must be considered, such as the gas species, level of accuracy, response time and overall cost. In situations where a rapid response, high accuracy at low gas concentration, and cost-effective solution are required, non-interactive optical gas sensors are preferred.

6.2 Non-dispersive infrared optical gas sensor

NDIR optical gas sensors detect the concentration by measuring and analysing the absorption of the incident IR radiation by the target gas. The basis of the sensor is that each gas species absorb IR radiation at different wavelengths. By emitting IR radiation into a gas volume and detecting the absorbed IR radiation, it is possible to determine the concentration of the gas.

A typical NDIR gas sensor configuration comprises of a known IR source, an optical gas cell or chamber, a detector, and associated electronic units. The IR radiation is launched into the gas chamber, where it is absorbed by the target gas. The unabsorbed radiation that reaches the detector is proportional to the concentration of the gas. The transmitted radiation from the source is then converted to an electrical signal. The principle of optical gas sensing is based on the Beer-Lambert law (125):

$$I = I_o e^{-\alpha l} \quad (6.1)$$

Where I_o is the incident light on the gas volume in the chamber, I is the measured light through the gas chamber, α is the gas absorption coefficient and l is the optical path length of the gas chamber.

The electrical unit processes the detected electronic signal, this processing involves amplification, filtering, analogue-to-digital conversion and further processing by a microcontroller. Firstly, the signal is amplified to a level which can be further processed, while a filter removes any unwanted noise. Then an analogue-to-digital converter (ADC) unit transforms the analogue

signal to a digital format which is used within the microcontroller. Finally, the microcontroller then further processes the signal using algorithms designed to translate the digital signal into a gas concentration measurement. The measurement is then output onto a user interface or sent onto a data logger for further use and analysis.

To enhance the measurement, the detector is positioned at the opposite end of the gas chamber from the IR source, demonstrated in Figure 6.3, to ensure the radiation passes through the full length of the gas chamber, increasing interactions with the target gas. Moreover, the chamber is often filled with a known reference gas, such as nitrogen, and a measurement is recorded as a reference to improve accuracy and reduce the impact of environmental factors such as temperature and humidity.

Figure 6.3: A standard NDIR gas sensor setup includes the infrared source, optical filter, detector, and gas concentration level within the cell. Depicted schematically to show the various components and their relationships to each other.

NDIR gas sensors offer a range of advantages for close-to-ambient gas sensing purposes. The ability to measure down to parts per Million (ppm) with high accuracy for a target gas species and the stability on a wide range of temperatures and humidity levels, make them well-suited for a

variety of commercial and industrial environments. Additionally, the small size achievable with compact design and ease of integration into make them an attractive choice in many gas sensing applications.

6.2.1 NDIR IR sources

In NDIR gas sensing, there are two main types of IR light sources used: MEMS thermal hotplate and semiconductor mid-IR light-emitting diodes (LEDs).

MEMS thermal micro hotplate emitters typically consist of suspended resistive heating elements in a silicon membrane, that can generate broadband infrared radiation when an electrical current is passed through them. The major advantages of micro hotplate emitters are the ease of manufacture and operation, allowing for a low-cost solution as a source for NDIR gas sensing. As well as their ability to be easily integrated into larger systems and stability over time. However, these sources can be relatively sizable when compared to alternatives and need continuous powering to stay at operating temperature.

Semiconductor III-V material LED sources, including aluminium gallium arsenide (AlGaAs) or Aluminium Indium Antimonide ($\text{Al}_x\text{In}_{1-x}\text{Sb}$), have a narrow IR spectral emission. The spectral profile can also be tuned for specific wavelengths to produce a narrow bandwidth source to minimise any unwanted noise. Due to this, these sources are suitable and often preferred for NDIR gas sensing. Their small size and low power consumption allow for portable, battery-powered gas detection. However, The output spectra can become susceptible to drift with time, meaning they can be less stable than thermal sources.

6.2.2 Non-Dispersive Infrared IR detectors

Similar to NDIR gas sensor sources, detectors typically use either thermal detection such as a thermopile or photonic detection such as semiconductor III-V materials as sensing elements.

Thermopile sensors are typically passive detectors that comprise multiple thermocouples connected in series, alternating between two dissimilar metals. When exposed to thermal radiation, a temperature gradient is produced across the thermopile regions. The temperature gradient is then converted into an electrical signal and with many thermocouples stacked together, a measurable signal response can be produced.

Semiconductor III-V material detectors, such as Indium Antimonide (InSb), work based on the photo-current effect. When incoming IR radiation strikes the detector, a current is produced proportional to the incident power of the radiation. When amplified, this current response can be used as a detection signal and processed to produce a measured spectral response.

6.2.3 Optical filtering

Optical filtering is an important measure in a gas sensor's selectivity, filtering the incoming radiation can offer better detection of the target gas with no crossover from neighbouring gas species. An optical filter is usually placed onto or immediately before the detector, as the source light passes through the optical gas chamber, the filter restricts the wavelength range seen by the detector, offering a more accurate measurement of the target gas. A bandpass filter tailors the light and restricts wavelength bands that are not of interest, this aids in the selectivity and reduces undesired crosstalk between gases. Typically, as only a narrow spectrum is needed,

a narrow band pass filter is the type chosen. However, there is a trade-off as optical filtering does lower the overall percentage of received light at the detector and can influence the sensitivity, filter design and gas sensor requirements must be considered.

6.2.4 Path length of optical chamber

The distance between the IR source and detector is known as the path length of the gas sensor. It plays an important role in the sensitivity of a gas sensor. In general, a longer path length allows for more gas absorption of the IR radiation due to a longer time spent in the gas volume. However, the longer the optical path length, the larger the gas chamber dimensions and subsequently the greater the overall gas sensor size becomes. This can lead to practical issues in certain applications where sensor size is a limiting factor. The path length must be considered from a practical standpoint as well as the final sensitivity required (132).

To increase the path length while maintaining a miniaturised-sized optic, a highly reflective optical coating, such as gold or aluminium, can be applied and the optic design be constructed to allow the reflection of light inside the gas chamber. This then extends the path length by reflecting IR light off the walls of the gas chamber multiple times, increasing the time from the source to the detector. The resulting measurement offers higher sensitivity and better accuracy at no extra optic size.

6.2.5 NDIR CO₂ gas sensing

For NDIR CO₂ gas sensing applications, the light source spectral output can be tailored to the major absorption wavelengths of CO₂ at 4.26 μm in

the mid-IR region (133). Similarly, the detector response can be optimised to be highly sensitive and selective at the major absorption wavelength for CO₂. The use of an optical filter centred at the CO₂ absorption wavelength between 4.2 and 4.6 μm can fine-tune the IR light received at the detector to better the selectivity of the gas sensor and improve the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

6.3 NDIR Gas sensor comparison for ISS plant study

For the plant study carried out in this work onboard the ISS it is crucial to have accurate and reliable CO₂ detection at close-to-ambient levels. As such, two NDIR gas sensors have been compared for CO₂ detection that is suited to this application. The first one is the narrow bandgap III-V LED light source and photodiode detector, produced by GSS Ltd, trademarked as COZIR. The second is a multi-gas sensor with a micro hotplate source and lead-selenide photodetector array, which was developed at the University of the West of Scotland.

The commercially available COZIR sensor has been designed with a “narrow” spectrum III-V LED light source and a photodiode detector. As a result of the narrow source-detector spectral product, there is no need for additional optical filtering and the optical path length of 70 mm is achieved with a highly reflective coated optical structure.

The multi-gas sensor is an in-house UWS fabricated gas sensor that uses a micro-hotplate as the IR source and a semiconductor III-V detector array. The use of a LVF placed between the source and detector gives spectral

discrimination per detector elements and facilitates the detection of multiple gases simultaneously. The optical structure uses mirrors and reflectors to direct the emitted IR to the sensors with a total path length of 60 mm.

The selected sensor from a comparison study of the COZIR and multi-gas sensor will be integrated into the experiment monitoring system for plant life growth chamber in microgravity. It is essential for accurate CO₂ levels to validate plant growth and development.

The NDIR multi-gas sensor design

The UWS fabricated NDIR multi-gas sensor uses a micro-hotplate as the IR source. The micro-hotplate is situated between silicon nitride substrates and utilises aluminium metal pads as the electrodes. When energised the resistive material heats and emits broadband IR emission and acts as a reliable blackbody source.

The IR radiation is guided by mirrors and reflectors to become incident on an LVF for a total path length of 60 mm. The filter then splits the light into various wavelengths onto a detector array and blocks all unwanted wavelengths. For CO₂ detection the filter only passes light centred at 4.26 μ m, this improves the accuracy and reliability of the CO₂ measurement.

The detector array uses lead selenide as the photoconductive sensor material, which can detect infrared radiation effectively in the 3-5 μ m region. The sensor's electrical conductivity changes in response to IR light exposure and can be amplified to produce a measurable signal. The generated signal is then further processed to give a precise measurement of the target gas concentration.

The schematic diagram, shown in Figure 6.4, depicts a basic illustration of

the sensor configuration for multi-gas detection using an LVF to separate the wavelengths of light per detector, tailored to different gases.

Figure 6.4: Schematic diagram of the gas sensor optic design. The sensor comprises a micro-hotplate source and a lead selenide sensor. A thin film optical filter is positioned between the source and detector to allow only the desired wavelength of light to pass through while blocking unwanted radiation.

The COZIR CO₂ gas sensor design

The commercially available COZIR NDIR CO₂ gas sensor is specifically designed for CO₂ detection (134). The NDIR gas sensor is a highly effective device for gas sensing, consisting of a specialized narrow bandgap III-V LED light source that emits mid-infrared radiation into an optical structure. As explained by Gibson and MacGregor (135), the diodes are fabricated using MBE and are based on a tertiary alloy of Al_xIn_{1-x}Sb. The optical structure, shown in Figure 6.5 forms a light path through the gas chamber, allowing for highly accurate detection. The emitted radiation is detected by an identical III-V photodiode in reverse bias, ensuring high precision and reliability. The sensor is available in two path lengths, 20 mm and 70 mm, providing flexibility for various applications. For near-ambient gas sensing applications, the longer 70 mm path length of the NDIR gas sensor is better suited due to its ability to measure a larger diffusion volume. The increased path length enables the sensor to detect trace concentrations of gases in the surrounding environment with higher accuracy and precision.

Figure 6.5: Schematic diagram of the COZIR 70 mm pathlength optical configuration CO₂ gas sensor, (106).

6.4 Modelling of in-house produced multi-gas sensor

To model the behaviour of an NDIR gas sensor, the spectral output of the source, the sensitivity and spectral response of the detector, the behaviour of the optical filter, the performance of the sensor with temperature shifts, and the effect of varying path length must be considered.

The sensor's modelling is carried out using a Mathcad 15.0 (136) model developed at the University of the West of Scotland. Mathcad 15.0 software provides an effective and versatile software for the complex modelling of the sensor. The gas absorption data is obtained from the HITRAN 2012 database, (137), through the Spectral Calc online spectral modelling tool, which extracts 600 data points of wavelength and absorption strength information for separate gases and imports directly into the Mathcad model.

6.4.1 Source spectral output

For the purposes of modelling simplicity, the custom doped polysilicon MEMS micro-hotplate that is used as the broadband IR source is approximated as a blackbody emitter, which radiates in all directions and is considered a point source.

According to Planck's law of electromagnetic radiation, the micro-hotplate's net black body radiation emitted into a hemisphere at a specific temperature T and wavelength λ can be determined by its net spectral radiant exitance, which is expressed in terms of power per unit area per wavelength

interval is given by:

$$W_{plank}(\lambda, T) = \frac{2\pi hc^2}{\lambda^5} \times \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda kT}} - 1} \quad (6.2)$$

Where, Planck's constant (h), the speed of light (c), Boltzmann's constant (k_B), and the wavelength of electromagnetic radiation (λ).

The total black body radiation emitted across the entire area of the micro-hotplate is integrated to approximate the net source spectral radiant power at 25°C, resulting in the modelled performance shown in Figure 6.6.

Figure 6.6: A MEMS-Based Micro Hotplate Model for CO₂ Gas Sensing. The figure depicts a MEMS-based micro hotplate with doped polysilicon as the active heating element, modelled as the broadband infrared source at 25C.

From the modelled results and Figure 6.6, the spectral output from the micro-hotplate blackbody source is among the highest at the target ab-

sorption wavelength of CO₂ at 4.26 μm. This supports the use of the micro-hotplate as the source material and that necessary interactions between the IR radiation and CO₂ molecules can take place and be detected by a sensor.

COZIR source comparison

By comparing the modelled micro-hotplate to the COZIR gas sensor LED source, it is clear that both sources offer high spectral output over the desired wavelengths for CO₂ detection. However, the COZIR produces a more tailored spectral shape for specifically *cO*₂ detection with a narrower spectrum, shown in Figure 6.7. This more concentrated spectral shape in terms of bandwidth across the 4.26 μm absorption band, offers higher spectral resolution which is vital to detect minute changes in the lower ppm, close-to-ambient levels.

Figure 6.7: COZIR LED measured spectral output.

6.4.2 Detector response

To assess the spectral response and temperature dependencies of the detecting sensor array which comprises 8 combined detectors, each with a size of 1.0×0.8 mm, a model of the D^* is constructed over the absorption band of CO_2 , from 2-5 μm . The D^* , shown in equation 6.3, is a merit used to evaluate the sensitivity and noise (including Johnson–Nyquist noise and dark current noise, which contribute to the detector’s overall noise floor) characteristics of a detector, the D^* assessment is wavelength and temperature dependent. A higher D^* value, the more sensitive the detector is to detect low-level signals with a low SNR. The D^* of the detector array is modelled at a temperature of 25°C and the resulting curve is plotted in

Figure 6.8, and represented as,

$$D^*(\lambda, T) = D_{PR} \times S_{PD}(\lambda, T), \quad (6.3)$$

where the parameter D_{PR} (Detectivity of the Photodetector Receiver) is influenced by various factors such as the spectral density of the noise of the photodetector, the area of the detector array element, and the bandwidth of detection and $S_{PD}(\lambda, T)$ which refers to the spectral power density of the detector, is a function of the detector responsivity.

Figure 6.8: Modelled detector response data.

Furthermore, the Mathcad model is extended to include varying temperatures, as the detector material is known to be sensitive to temperature fluctuations. The model is extended to include temperatures of -25°C and 50°C that are presented in figure 6.9

Figure 6.9: Modelled detector response data for temperatures of -25°C , 25°C , and 50°C .

The modelled response from the detector array demonstrates the high-level sensitivity at the $4.26\ \mu\text{m}$ absorption band for CO_2 . When modelling is extended to include a temperature range, the sensor behaves better at room temperature compared to the extremes examined at -25°C and 50°C . The result suits the application in which the sensor will be examining the CO_2 level on board the ISS.

COZIR detector comparison

Comparing the COZIR detector to the multi-gas sensor detector array, the COZIR has a relatively high-intensity peak at the CO_2 absorption wavelength, allowing for adequate interaction and detection of the CO_2 molecules. There is a feature present at the $2.8\ \mu\text{m}$ wavelength in Figure

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6.10. This is characteristic of water absorption. However, this is due to the measurement system setup and operation and should be factored into the interpretation of the detector response spectra.

Figure 6.10: Measured photodiode spectral response with a feature observed at the 2.8 μm.

6.4.3 Thermopile detector enhancement

The work carried out in Chapter 5 to enhance a thermopile detector for increased sensitivity to IR radiation was highly successful with an average boost in an output voltage of 220%. A BBA multilayer optical coating increased the absorptance in the 2.5-20 μm range while minimising the reflected radiation.

Comparison to COZIR

Ultimately the boosted performance of the thermopile gave a D^* value of $1.9 \times 10^8 \text{cm}\sqrt{\text{HzW}^{-1}}$ (116) and the COZIR photodiode has a detectivity D^* value of $2 \times 10^8 \text{cm}\sqrt{\text{HzW}^{-1}}$ (135), the higher sensitivity COZIR sensor is more suited to lower levels of CO_2 detection.

6.4.4 Source-Detector product

The source-detector product gives the overall sensor accuracy and sensitivity. Accurate gas measurement can be achieved with a selective source-detector product aimed at the major absorption line wavelength of the target gas. The source-detector product model incorporates the spectral response from the source and the detector response from the sensor to give the overall product shown by Equation 6.4 and in Figure 6.11.

The multi-gas sensor is modelled to accomplish this with a micro-hotplate source and a lead selenide photodetector both operating in the 2-5 μm

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range.

$$SR = SR_{Source} \times S_{Detector} \quad (6.4)$$

SR_{Source} represents the spectral response of the microhotplate at room temperature, while $S_{Detector}$ represents the spectral sensitivity of the photodiode photodetector at the same temperature. The photodiode photodetector has a calculated detectivity of $2.93 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}\sqrt{\text{HzW}^{-1}}$.

Figure 6.11: Modelled spectral response from the source and detector.

From Figure 6.11, the source-detector product offers high sensitivity in the 3-4.5 μm region, where the gasses of interest have significant absorption. With the use of optical filtering, this response can be tailored for CO_2 gas detection at the 4.26 μm absorption wavelength, allowing for accurate gas sensing for many applications.

COZIR source-detector product comparison

The COZIR sensor has been designed and constructed with a highly selective source-detector product profile aimed at CO₂ detection. As opposed to the multigas sensor, the COZIR has been only one gas species to detect and Figure 6.12 shows the profile. The CO₂ absorption profile from Figure 6.1 fits precisely within the area under the profile of the curve. This produces a highly accurate and reproducible measurement without the extra steps of optical filtering.

Figure 6.12: Measured spectral response from COZIR LED/PDs (138).

6.4.5 Bandpass filtering

The multi-gas sensor required optical filtering for accurate measurement of the target gas. In order to simplify the modelling process the LVF is approximated to a Gaussian distribution and the central wavelength is at the absorption wavelength of CO₂.

Figure 6.13: Modelled bandpass filter centred at the MIR CO₂ absorption line

The modelled source-detector-filter product, presented in Figure 6.14 (135), is heavily narrowed and only spans the absorption wavelength of CO₂ (117). The modelled sensor can now be used as a reliable tool for CO₂ detection.

COZIR filter comparison

The COZIR sensor has been through several optimisation and tuning steps to produce a sensor with no need for optical filtering. The narrow spectral output from the COZIR source combined with the reverse bias-tuned photodiode detector response, produces a narrowband sensor at the CO₂ wavelength. The source and detector response act together to remove the need for optical filtering, this gives a simpler, less expensive design.

6.4.6 Comparison of spectral performance with CO₂ gas absorption lines

The multi-gas sensor has the ability to detect the absorption lines of many gasses using an LVF. This approach can be highly effective for multiple gases with multiple detectors. However, this is also suited to CO₂ absorption wavelength with filtering. The simulated results of the source-detector-filter product with the CO₂ gas absorption are presented in figure 6.14.

The design of the COZIR gas sensor produces a narrow spectrum source emission and detection, this has been specifically designed for CO₂ detection at 4.26 um. The resulting tuned sensor, concentrated at the CO₂ absorption band, has a high SNR and good sensitivity. The narrow bandwidth produced without optical filtering and absorption of CO₂ are shown in figure 6.15.

Figure 6.14: Modelled spectral response from the source and detector with CO_2 gas absorption line present (134).

6.4.7 Sensor construction

Injection moulded optic

The multi-gas sensor incorporates optical filtering that enables spectra discrimination to individual detectors. The sensor housing is a three-piece folded Schwarzschild-based optical dome design with a path length of 70 mm. The optic is made from an injection moulded blend of polycarbonate and platable acrylonitrile butadiene styrene. The optical design of the Schwarzschild dome collects the source light, directing through a series of mirrors and reflectors to magnify the profile to match the grading of an LVF and detectors in the detector array, as shown in Figure 6.4.

Conversely, the COZIR sensor does not use any optical filtering due to the narrow LED/PD bandwidth. However, the housing, shown in figure 6.5,

Figure 6.15: Measured spectral response from the COZIR source and detector with CO_2 gas absorption line present.

used is also injection moulded and a highly reflective gold coating with a reflectivity of around 98% to 99% is deposited onto the internal walls of the sensor to offer a longer pathlength of 70 mm in a compact structure (138).

Electronics and Signal processing

The Multigas sensor controls up to eight channels for gas detection combined with optical filtering and controls the micro-hotplate operation. The combined systems utilise a 16-bit ADC and a 32-bit digital to analogue converter (DAC) to account for temperature offset fluctuations. An ultra-low power Field Programmable Gate Array field programmable gate array (FPGA) controls the ADC, DAC, input switching multiplexer, and hot

plate pulse timing. In order to reduce power consumption the FPGA is operated at 42 MHz, this allows accurate sensor control with minimal power usage. The resulting sensor is of low power, high reliability and can capture accurate gas readings.

The COZIR CO₂ sensor comprises of off-shelf cost-effective components and easily available hardware to achieve a compact signal processing final unit, that can measure accurate gas concentrations at low-power consumption from the LED/PD octopair. The gas sensing signal process procedure has been developed and implemented by Gas Sensing Solutions Ltd (GSS) which has been specifically designed for CO₂ detection using the LED/PD octopair. The process involves sending a rapid pulse, dictated by a microcontroller unit (MCU), to the LED via a gain stage intermittently. The controlled IR radiation released strikes the photodiode (PD) where the signal is amplified and then captured by the MCU ADC for further processing. The processed data is converted to a measured CO₂ level in the gas housing chamber. The process is carried out in real-time and compensations are made for the temperature changes and intensities of IR radiation incident on the PD.

Power consumption

The design and operation of the Multi-gas sensor allow for a low power-consuming unit with usage in the milli Joules range. The gas sampling rate per minute and the frequency of source pulsing determine the power consumption cost. A lower limit should be maintained for accurate and reliable gas concentration measurement. Operating at 1 Hz and toggling the hotplate between on and off states, the energy can be below 13 mW. The overall power consumption for each gas of interest depends on the

sampling rate of the detector and is heavily dependent on the integration time of the measurement.

The COZIR CO₂ sensor when in continuous operation mode has a power usage of 3.3 mW using the LED/detector device array. When in an alternative pulsed mode, draws approx. 1 mJ of energy to wake and warm up the sensor, record a measurement of the gas, and power down to an idle state, this is termed the ultra low power (ULP) mode.

6.5 Results

6.5.1 Multigas sensor results

The multi-gas sensor provides low-level concentration detection, CO₂ detection as low as 500 ppm. With the detectable change of concentration measured 200 ppm. In turn, the gas sensor can distinguish changes in gas concentration of CO₂ as low as 200ppm. Considering the noise within the setup, the measurements were sufficient to affect the final sensitivity achieved. To suppress this, long-term averaging was adopted that reduced the noise by 1/3 to 10 or fewer ADC counts. To further reduce the noise, steps could be taken to perform real-time averaging combined with improved processing, to improve the accuracy of the final sensor concentration results. In summary, the multi-gas sensor was able to detect changes in CO₂ concentration when tested. However, further enhancements are needed to develop the system into a more sensitive gas sensor with high accuracy of detection.

6.5.2 COZIR CO₂ gas sensor

The COZIR CO₂ gas sensor achieved high accuracy and sensitivity at a range of CO₂ concentration levels, specifically at close to ambient levels. The hardware and scheduling of the sensor electronics allowed for a long lifetime device with low power mode for energy preservation. Due to these reasons the sensor has applications within industrial settings, public buildings and as a portable wearable device.

6.5.3 Selection for ISS space study

For the plant development study onboard the ISS, both sensor performances have been investigated with the aim to detect CO₂ in a plant growth chamber. A requirement of the plant study is the detection of accurate CO₂ changes at close to ambient levels for a prolonged time. Comparing each sensor, the COZIR CO₂ sensor proved the more sensitive gas sensor, accomplishing detection as low as 400 ppm. The sensor also provides a more accurate change in ppm and stability with time. Consequently, the COZIR was chosen to be the gas sensor for the pace-based plant experiment aboard the ISS. The lower level of CO₂ ppm detection, low power consumption and extended lifetime was important factors in the plant growth experiment.

6.6 Conclusion

The multi-gas assembled sensor proved that it could detect CO₂ concentration changes and measure down to approximately 500 ppm, with detection of concentration changes as low as 200 ppm, however suffered from high noise within the sensor system which affected the final results reported and

6.6. CONCLUSION

overall sensitivity of the sensor. The COZIR CO₂ gas sensor has high sensitivity and accuracy, measuring down to 400 ppm with stability at the lower CO₂ levels. Moreover, the long battery-life and ULP mode was suited to the plant experiment that will be battery operated. The COZIR sensor was superior in these respects to the multi-gas and was selected for the ISS space-based plant experiment.

Chapter 7

Plant life selection, experiment assembly and testing

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the considerations and constraints of space-based experimentation are explored, as well as the design and construction of experiments focused on plant growth. Also, discussed is the importance of conducting plant “hardiness” experiments and the use of a box test to evaluate the effects of space-based conditions on plant growth. Finally, the results of an earth-based 7-day trial are presented and conclusions are drawn about the baselining experiment.

7.2 Considerations and constraints of space-based experimentation

To conduct an experiment on board the ISS or in any microgravity environment is a complex operation with multiple steps and a wide range of factors have to be considered (139). The consideration must include factors such as project objectives, the experiment's design, safety, budget, and scheduling. The chapter explores each of these factors and aims to design an experiment for space launch and have an earth-based control experiment conducted.

7.2.1 Safety considerations

Due to the challenging nature of the ISS environment and plant growth in micro-gravity, there must be specific safety considerations. Safety is the primary consideration (140) with all activities and experiments on the ISS. The major sources of threat with a plant growing experiment are the risks of organisms or pathogens contamination and carbon dioxide leaks.

Risk of contamination

From the moment the experiment is unloaded from the launch module and onboarded to the ISS, the biggest threat to astronaut safety and the integrity of the space station is unwanted organisms or pathogens being introduced (141). This can be from the plant life itself, the growth media or the experiment setup. A non-toxic and non-allergenic plant species is favoured to minimise contamination and related astronaut health risks. The plant growth media taken on board should be free of both bacteria

and microorganisms to lessen the risk of disease spread.

Carbon dioxide leaks

The plant experiment is packaged with above ambient levels of CO₂, ambient typically between 400 ppm (142), to exploit accelerated plant growth in exaggerated CO₂ levels (143), the plant study was packaged with 1500 ppm level. Even with the elevated CO₂ levels, there is no urgent threat to astronaut health onboard. Moreover, CO₂ is actively scrubbed out of the ISS environment. If the experiment box were to become damaged and rupture causing exposure, the minimal CO₂ exposure would be scrubbed out of the atmosphere, like exhaled CO₂ by the crew aboard (144).

Experiment double sealing system

In order to mitigate the risks of contamination or CO₂ leaks, the plant experiment is enclosed within a double-sealed container and all astronaut interactions are carried out with one level of containment in place at all times. This includes interactions such as project set-up, battery changes and SD-card removal.

The highest-ranking hazards have been examined and the safety precautions/practices in place are sufficient to minimise the crew and space station risk. Before launch or loading onto a spacecraft, a final leak test is conducted and acts as a fail-safe method to validate the experiment sealing. Specifically, this is a CO₂ leak test and detection using the experiment CO₂ sensor.

7.2.2 Technical considerations

The technical challenges involved in space payload structure, development, and management, combined with the high costs associated with space transport and ISS research set limitations on the experiment design. Moreover, there are considerations and limitations set by International Space School Educational Trust (ISSET) and Nanoracks (facilitators of the experiment to the ISS). These limitations are not universal to all space-based experimentation but must be adhered to within this study.

Experiment Cannot Be Returned

The experiment cannot be returned to Earth as the costs of returning on an Earth-bound spacecraft are extremely high and stretch beyond the project budgets. Instead, the experimental setup will be destroyed after the total trial has taken place. The remaining hardware is loaded onto a separate spacecraft and disposed of in a similar way as other ISS waste. The destruction of the hardware does not allow an identical control experiment to be replicated on Earth or any further investigations after the space-based research has concluded. All returned data is via the crew's photography and stored data on memory cards.

Interaction Activities

During the experiment trial, there are specific planned moments, known as interaction events, when astronauts will interfere with the experiments. These interaction events are 20-minute periods where project-related activities can be carried out, such as battery changes, data recording periods or photography sessions. The interaction events are short and have to be

completed within the designated time and must not exceed a total of five events throughout the trial.

Simple experimental design

The experiment design must be simple but also robust enough to last the stress brought on by any cold storage events prior to space flight, the transport to the launch site, load onto and launch within a space shuttle. The steps in the experiment set-up put a lot of pressure on the experiment and increase the chance of damage or failure. To reduce the risk of damage, the experiment should minimise the number of potential points of failure by utilising a simple design. This is critically important with experimenting on the ISS as there is limited capacity for duplicate experiments. The logistical steps and total cost must also be heavily considered. This comprises the final weight and dimensions of the experiment, set-up time, rocket launch and onboard maintenance or interactions. Therefore, experiment design is a crucial factor in this study.

Experiment Timing

The experiment timing is critical to the overall success of the study. The launch schedule and plant growth stage immediately prior to the launch must align. The launch timetable must take the space station's availability and the resources onboard the ISS needed to support the experiment into consideration. Moreover, the experiment duration has to be considered as the crew availability or any planned maintenance stages. This includes all time for experiment setup, running and closing of the trial. Also, the potential for setbacks and delays, such as cold storage, has to be explored to satisfy NASA's expectations, and for the experiment to be launched to

the ISS. Finally, the total time taken from closing the experiment trial and concluding results to be returned to Earth must be evaluated, as this is a crucial step in the analysis and evaluation. Thus, a detailed, well-timed launch schedule is critical for a successful experiment.

7.2.3 Scientific considerations

The scientific considerations are determined by the experimental setup and design. The major scientific consideration is the value of the data collected, quantifiable data is the major priority of the experiment design.

Quantifiable data

Quantifiable data supports all analytical techniques and makes for developing sound scientific discoveries or studies. However, within this project, there are constraints on both the high cost and bulky high-quality equipment that would stretch beyond the budgetary limits of this research and are substantial obstacles to quantifying science on board the ISS.

7.3 Plant identification

Choosing a suitable plant for conducting an experiment on the ISS is an extremely important factor in the overall success of the plant monitoring experiments.

The selection of an appropriate plant is a multi-step decision which must include the scientific and logistical features of the plant life. The plant has to survive the impact of microgravity and be well-suited to the ISS environment or possess qualities that are suitable for study in a closed sealed growth chamber system (145). Moreover, a consideration for plant mass and volume must be included, and how the facilities on board can support plant growth and monitoring during the trial. Any plant life chosen will be treated for unwanted micro-organisms or bacteria and contained in double-sealed packaging to reduce the chance of contamination. The plant chosen will also have to endure potential delay stages or cold storage if there are any interruptions to the launch schedule, preparation and packaging, and survive the stresses of the launch itself and the entirety of the trial on-board. As the trial time is finite, a fast-growing plant which can achieve quick growth and adaptability to any cold storage delays and microgravity conditions should be selected. An ideal candidate for the experiment is a fast-growing, low-maintenance, lightweight “hardy” nutrient-dense (Vitamin A, Vitamin C, and Vitamin K) green plant which is a good source of antioxidants. Based on these criteria several plant species are identified:

- *Ocimum basilicum* (Basil)
- *Valerianella locusta* (corn salad or lamb’s lettuce)
- *Brassica oleracea* (Kale)

- *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* (wild rocket)
- *Beta vulgaris* subsp. *vulgaris* (perpetual spinach)

7.4 Experiment design and construction

To be launched the payload must be within strict requirements. The final experiment design must be lightweight and fully contained in a single launch module. In this study, the volume given for the launch module has a maximum size of $10 \times 10 \times 15$ cm. This has to be considered in the designing and testing stages of the experimental setup, the experiment has also to be protected from damage and the high stresses of launch and transportation. This challenge is compounded as the experiment consists of delicate sensors, sensitive components and measuring instrumentation that are vital to the overall success of the monitoring experiment. It is essential that the final designs, construction and testing have considered the restricted space available and the severe conditions of launch and transportation, as well as the need to include all necessary equipment to monitor growth and development.

7.4.1 Experiment box design

The most major design consideration is the miniaturised launch module that dictated the dimensions of the experiment, the experiment should easily slide in and out of the launch module. Due to this, the ultimate dimensions of the experiment box available are $9.25 \times 9.25 \times 12$ cm and it must be a self-contained, hermetically sealed container for deployment in the ISS for safety considerations. The material that comprises the experi-

ment housing should be lightweight and robust to endure the total travel to the ISS. As a result, acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) was chosen (146). This was also selected as the material can be 3D printed into strong structures. The ability to design and 3D print makes the experiment design process smoother with quick and cheap iterations of design changes until the box fits the needs of a plant growth chamber. Also, the cost involved in generating new designs for testing or final revisions is low compared with other materials (147). The design of the $9.25 \times 9.25 \times 12$ cm experiment box must include all sensors, plant life, growth media, LED lighting SD memory card and power supply. To maximise plant growing area and include the highest number of growing plants, all sensors and LED lighting are on a removable lid. On the reverse side of the lid is a power source and an SD card was secured. This design is shown in Figure 7.1

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Figure 7.1: Expanded experiment box design for plant growth in space. The $9.25 \times 9.25 \times 12$ cm box contains all necessary components for successful plant growth, including sensors, growth media, LED lighting, SD memory card, and power supply. The removable lid with integrated sensors and LED lighting allows for maximum plant growing area, while the reverse side houses the power source and SD card for secure data storage.

The power source and all associated electronics are attached solely to the experiment box lid. This serves as a safety feature as if there was any damage to occur to the body of the experiment box prior to space flight, the box body can be swapped out without changes to the experiment design. A plant “pillow” is included in the body of the box which hosts the growth media and plant life, this is fully removable by design and can also be swapped out at any point prior to rocket launch. To hold the plant pillow

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a second 3D-printed container holds the pillow in place with struts and the whole container slides into the experiment box body. The final compact assembled design is shown in figure 7.2

Figure 7.2: Schematic of the assembled design for the 9.25x9.25x12cm experiment box for plant growth in microgravity. The removable lid houses all electronics including the light-emitting diode lighting, sensors, and power supply, serving as a backup option in case of damage to the body of the experiment box.

7.4.2 Plant “pillow” construction and transplanting

A plant pillow is a container that can be used to hold and grow plants. The pillow is a sealed structure that holds the plant growing medium, such as soil, water and supports the plant and its roots during growth (148). The pillow can be made to custom sizes depending on the limits of space and the number of plants to be grown. Within this experiment, the plant pillow must fit within the experiment box body and support a number of plants for monitoring. The material used should be strong, durable but flexible and lightweight. Strong woven cotton was selected to house the soil-water mixture and plant food essential for plant growth and development. As the plant pillow and its contents will experience microgravity, it has to be secured to the base of the plant experiment box body. The second 3D printed container or “growth chamber” is used to secure the plant pillow inside the experiment box and is shown in Figure 7.3. The design slides into the experiment box with supporting struts to secure the plant pillow prior to transplantation.

Plant “pillow” construction procedure:

- Autoclave and dry topsoil to be used as growth media.
- Prepare growth media by mixing the 100 g (sterile, dry) plus 100 milliliters of distilled water.
- Form a tube shape from the woven cotton material.
- Tie a secure knot at the narrower end, then stretch the tube over a wide-mouthed plastic/metal cylinder, such as a beaker, to support it and make filling with solid media easier.
- Add the weighed media to the inside of the woven cotton tube, with

Figure 7.3: The design of the experiment box for growing plants in microgravity. The plant pillow containing the plant life and growth media is securely held in place by the growth chamber which slides into the experiment box. Supporting struts ensure proper positioning of the plant pillow prior to transplantation.

the knotted/foot end at the base.

- Transfer the filled plant pillow to the growth chamber, that will house it. Then add distilled water and allow the substrate to hydrate.
- Cut the woven cotton tube 2 cm above the surface of the growth media, then sew a running stitch all the way around, at about 1 cm from the edge. This produces a sealed woven cotton square planting area.
- Pierce a hole in the top surface of the cotton material to create an opening for transplant. Each hole has to be widened to accommodate the width of the seedling's roots. Each seedling is transplanted, taking

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care to avoid damaging the roots or breaking the stem, from growth soil to plant pillow growth media. The seedling's roots were then eased into the hole, and each root is carefully 'winded' through the hole, into the growth medium beneath. The surrounding soil gently tamped down around the roots, closing the widened aperture in the cotton and ensuring good root contact with the soil.

7.4.3 Experiment Hardware

Carbon Dioxide sensor

From Chapter 6, the gas sensor chosen for the launch was the COZIR CO₂ sensor due to the low levels of ppm detection with higher accuracy.

RH and Temperature sensor

A RH sensor is a device which is used to measure the relative humidity in the air present within the immediate environment. The sensor works to measure the level of moisture in the air and compares this result against how much moisture the air can hold before saturation. The ratio is expressed as a percentage, this is the resulting RH percentage. The RH sensor used in this study is an HDC1080 Digital Humidity with Temperature Sensor. The performance of the sensor was tested within an environmental chamber at the levels expected on board the ISS. The test was conducted at 22°C, the results are plotted in figure 7.4.

Optimal RH for leafy green plant growth and development has been investigated and found to be between 50-70% (149). Within this range, the correct amount of moisture is in the environment allowing the plant to absorb necessary water and nutrients to promote growth and development. If the RH is too low, the plant can become stressed as it dries out, this has a direct impact on growth and leads to leaf drop and wilting. Conversely, if too high, fungus and bacteria can grow and cause the plants to become unhealthy or diseased, leading to plant death. When maintaining RH between the optimal levels, the chances of successful growth and normal development of the plants are highest. Throughout the testing, the majority of the RH time series for the sensor and the environmental cham-

Figure 7.4: RH testing for the HDC1080 sensor with an environmental chamber as a control to verify its performance under conditions similar to those on the ISS, set at a constant temperature of 22 deg Celsius

ber are close to one another, often overlapping. The deviations from one another are generally less than 5%.

The recordings measured from the sensor agree with the recordings from the environmental chamber. The differences observed are largely within 5% and have instances of overlap between both measurements.

Real Time clock

A real time clock (RTC) chip is a device which is used to keep a record of the date and time, even if there is power loss. A standard technique is to use a quartz crystal oscillator to keep the time elapsed and a battery-powered secondary unit to maintain the time elapsed when the device is not energised. The RTC chip used within this study was a DS3231MPMB1 Peripheral Module. A microcontroller connected to the RTC unit directs time-based functions, like setting the LED lighting on/off schedule and time stamps all data recordings made by any sensor. This allows for a clear time series by correlating the results with the time of collection, simplifying the analysis and enhancing the understanding of conditions within the experiment box.

LED wavelength selection

The wavelengths of light incident on plant life have a direct impact on the plant's growth stages, development and overall health. Leafy green plants require both the blue and red ends of the spectrum to grow optimally. The blue wavelengths are responsible for promoting vegetative growth and the red wavelengths promote healthy green leaf growth (150). LEDs can provide both the red and blue ends of the spectrum energy efficiently and are a cost-effective lightweight option that suits the considerations of space deployment (151). The narrow spectral output produced is well suited to leafy green plant growth (152) and has been proven to be very well absorbed by plant life (peak wavelengths for chlorophyll absorption) (153), leading to healthy mature plants. LEDs also produce minimal heat and suit the compact nature of the experiment setup, by not having significant influence of environment temperatures, unlike other sources of visible light (154). In

turn, this improves the reliability of data captured and conclusions drawn. Given the above, LED wavelengths chosen for plant illumination are 450 nm blue light and 660 nm red light (153).

LED lighting schedule

Leafy green plant life also requires darkness to grow and thrive. Important physiological processes take place only in darkness, such as growth hormone regulation and cell recovery/repair (81). During dark instances, plants encounter a process called photoperiodism, this process is the response of a plant to the length of darkness compared with daylight (155). This process is responsible for triggering changes in plant growth and development, such as the initiation of flowering or the formation of tubers. Plants also undergo a process called photorespiration, which is a metabolic process that helps to remove excess carbon dioxide from the plant cells. This process is important for maintaining the plant's energy balance and preventing damage to the plant's cells (156). Moreover, the period of darkness allows the plant to repair or replace cells, synthesise hormones and prepare for the next growth period. As a result, an on/off schedule of LED illumination is the best option for ensuring optimal growth and development (157). The length of 8 hours off with plants in total darkness and 16 hours of direct red/blue lighting for optimal growth and development was chosen.

Data collection

A data logger is a device that can store information and create records with time. A data logger can be used to record various data types and can store multiple at one time, such as temperature, RH, CO₂ level and time. The data is then stored on a non-volatile memory, this can be an

SD-card or similar storage device. This allows the data to be collected, stored, and retrieved for analysis later. Typically, the non-volatile memory is fully removable from the data logger and can be inserted into a computer to access the recorded and stored data.

Power delivery method

Power is a highly valuable and crucial resource aboard the ISS. The main power source available is generated by high-efficiency solar cell arrays on the outside of the station. It is a limited supply and all the stations' equipment runs from it. The systems and equipment must be as energy efficient as possible to conserve the shared power. The station can deliver power from the solar cells to USB ports around the station. However, it is extremely costly to do so as this requires more electricity to be generated to replace any used. Moreover, the energy generated is to support and power critical systems such as life support systems, propulsion systems, air scrubbing systems and other vital functions. Therefore, these are always prioritised and the use of USB power to power additional experiments is restricted. The only other power source is battery power that is carried to the station on resupply missions by cargo spacecraft such as the SpaceX Dragon, the Cygnus spacecraft, and the Russian Progress spacecraft. The resupply missions also deliver fresh or frozen foods, water, apparatus, and other supplies that need replenishing based on use. The battery cells are stored in separate compartments when launched and during transport for spacecraft safety. Within the station, these are readily used as on Earth or integrated into the power system. As there is no access to the restricted USB port power, the experiment in this study only has access and must run on battery power supplied by resupply missions. The experiment will be launched on a resupply mission but batteries are packaged in a separate

part of the spacecraft, and cannot be loaded into the experiment body. Any batteries in the experiment will be removed pre-launch. The RTC must have the battery removed pre-flight and as this is within the experiment box, it cannot be replaced when on the ISS. Opening the experiment box would be a zero-containment level task, exposing the box contents directly to the space station environment and violating the safety conditions. However, the RTC unit can function without a separate battery and only suffer inaccurate real-time date and time. The unit can timestamp the collected sensor data with an aggregated time since initial activation.

Total trial time onboard ISS

A major consideration is the time available per experiment to be conducted. As the experiment time increases in number of days so does the total cost of the study. This can create a challenge for experiments that require a longer duration to see results or collect data. The experiment design can be planned to minimise the time scales and maximise the available time allowed; this can be examined by running Earth-based trials and often involves experiment designs that can be set up quickly and run instantly, with minimal crew involvement. Furthermore, an experiment that is automated is preferred to reduce the crew's interaction events and time per event. The total experimental period given for this experiment is 7-10 days and there is no possibility to run on USB power or for the experiment hardware to be returned, apart from the experiment SD memory card. The launch schedule is managed by NASA and considers:

- The readiness of the project
- The readiness of the spacecraft and its payloads

- The availability of the launch vehicle
- The availability of the launch site and support facilities
- The alignment of the planets or other celestial bodies for interplanetary missions
- The weather forecast at the launch site
- The availability of the ground tracking and communication network
- The availability of the control and command centres

Final experiment box design and construction

The final experiment box construction, shown in Figure 7.5, has considered the limited space in the payload module, the limited power options for the entire experiment electronics, the limited time available to study plant growth in microgravity, the wavelengths and time schedule of light and climate in the immediate growing environment necessary for optimal plant growth and development. Also of major importance, the final design has considered the safety of the crew and station and the method to return quantifiable data from all sensors. Finally, the time of launch has been considered taking into account uncertainties due to current world conflicts.

Figure 7.5: The final design of the experiment box for studying plant growth, taking into account various constraints such as limited space in the payload module, power options, time for the experiment, optimal growing environment, crew safety and data return method.

7.5 Plant “hardiness” experiments

To determine the ideal plant that is best suited to experimenting in micro-gravity conditions on board the ISS, a comparison study was conducted and included several plant species. The five species chosen for this comparison were: *Ocimum basilicum* (Basil), *Valerianella locusta* (corn salad or lamb’s lettuce), *Brassica oleracea* (Kale), *Diplotaxis tenuifolia* (wild rocket), and *Beta vulgaris* subsp. *vulgaris* (perpetual spinach). All five plant types were tested based on a variety of criteria: growth rate, adaptability to the conditions on board the station, ability to withstand transport and cold storage and resistance to stress. Other than the plant’s physiological factors, the nutritional components of the plants, the benefits of the plant as a food source and the potential hazards to the crew were also considered.

7.5.1 Cold storage simulation

As there may be delays in launch dates due to launch recycling or unforeseen issues, the plant life may be exposed to cold storage until the issues are resolved. A standard durability test, known as a “cold stow” simulation can be carried out to determine which plant life has the best stress resistance. All plant species selected underwent a 28-day test. This was carried out in total darkness at a constant temperature between 2-6°Celsius. Each species was checked at days 0, 7, 14, 21 and finally 28, results of the completed test are presented in table 7.1.

Plant species	Colour	Wilting	leaf drop	Rot
Basil	Brown	yes	1	no
Lettuce	Yellowing	no	0	yes
Kale	Green	no	0	no
Rocket	Yellowing	yes	0	no
Spinach	Yellow	yes	0	no

Table 7.1: 28-day cold storage simulation results on various plant species.

The results from the cold stow simulation showed that almost all of the five plant species showed some signs of stress but to a varying degree. The Basil plant suffered the most with brown leaves, wilting, and rot present. This is a sign of the plant’s health declining, any additional time in the cold storage conditions may seriously damage the plant. The plant may also struggle to return to normal growth and development after any cold stow event. The lettuce plant showed signs of distress with yellowing leaves and early signs of rot but had no wilting or leaf drop. This may have been the beginning of infection or disease. Rocket and Spinach were also yellowing and wilted, but no leaf drop and no rot was present. These plants may be suitable for cold storage, transport, and study. Kale outperformed all other plant species, with green leaves and no wilting, leaf drop, or signs of rot. This indicates the plant has not suffered any issues due to cold stow

7.5. PLANT “HARDINESS” EXPERIMENTS

and is still healthy to be studied after any delay events and transport to the ISS.

In summary, the Kale plant species was the only plant to show no signs of deterioration. All other plant species suffered from some form of leaf discolouration, wilting, leaf drop or signs of rot.

7.5.2 LED wavelength and schedule testing

To identify the plant species best suited to the conditions within the experiment box setup, all species underwent scheduled wavelength specific LED testing. The experiment used red/blue wavelength LEDs in and 8 hours off and 16 hours on cycle. This acts as a simulation for day and night conditions on Earth and provides the plants with a natural schedule to carry out physiological processes.

Figure 7.6: Day 0 comparison of 5 Plant Species under Different LED Wavelength and Light Schedule for Optimal Growth. The experiment aimed to determine the ideal plant species for growth in the experiment box under red and blue LED lights, with a cycle of 8 hours off and 16 hours on to mimic day and night conditions.

The goal of the experiment was to identify the plant life best suited to the LED wavelengths and the scheduled light pattern for promoting growth and development. The experiment was conducted over 28 days and the plants were observed for changes in their growth patterns, number of leaves, plant height, and overall health.

7.5. PLANT “HARDINESS” EXPERIMENTS

Observations	Basil	Lettuce	Kale	Rocket	spinach
Colour	Yellowing	Green	Green	Green	Green
Leaves per plant	3	2	6	2	3
Growth (cm)	1.5	0.8	3	1.9	2

Table 7.2: Observation Results of the LED Wavelength and Schedule Testing for Different Plant Species. The table shows the results of the LED wavelength and schedule testing on five different plant species (Basil, Lettuce, Kale, Rocket, and Spinach) in terms of their colour, number of leaves per plant, growth, and overall health. The observations were made after the completion of the LED illumination schedule of 8 hours off and 16 hours on.

The results of the LED wavelength and the scheduled light pattern testing showed that the Basil showed some signs of stress with the yellowing of leaves, three leaves per plant, with a total growth of 1.5cm. The Basil species had fair growth but discolouration indicating poor health. The lettuce showed minimal growth of 0.8cm and only two leaves per plant but exhibits green leaves. Kale was the fastest-growing plant with a growth rate of 3 and had the largest leaf area. It also had the most leaves per plant at a total of six leaves with large leaf areas. The rocket had a fair growth rate of 1.9cm, with narrow green leaves, and only two leaves per plant. Spinach displayed the second fastest growth rate and leaf area with a total of three leaves per plant.

In summary, based on the observations the Kale plant species performed the best with the fastest growth rate and largest leaf area. The spinach plant showed the second-best growth and leaf area, all other species had minimal growth rates or signs of ill health.

Figure 7.7: Day 21 comparison of 5 Plant Species under Different LED Wavelength and Light Schedule for Optimal Growth. The experiment aimed to determine the ideal plant species for growth in the experiment box under red and blue LED lights, with a cycle of 8 hours off and 16 hours on to mimic day and night conditions.

7.5.3 Growth media testing

To identify the best growth media for the plant growth experiment on board the ISS, common growth media underwent testing. The growth media tested included soil, vermiculite, and a soilless mix, known as hydrogel. From a safety perspective and to protect the ISS environment from pathogens and bacteria, all soils are treated prior to deployment. The method of treating the growth media is the autoclaving process. This activity sterilises using high-pressure and high-temperature steam to kill any microorganisms present in the growth media (158). The process includes storing the growth media in a container, often a plastic box or bag, and introducing the container into the autoclave, where the container is heated to a high temperature and pressure for a set time, typically 20 minutes. The pressures and temperatures kill any unwanted bacteria or microorganisms

7.5. PLANT “HARDINESS” EXPERIMENTS

within the growth media. After the autoclave process, the media is cooled to the desired temperature and is free of contamination and ready for sterile use. The process has a direct impact on plant growth and development, it removes any harmful pathogens or organisms that may harm the plant by causing diseases. Moreover, it protects the integrity of the ISS and all the other experiments on board if there were any zero-level exposures. From the observations of the plant growth media comparison, leafy green plants in soil performed the best out of all included. The plants in the soil had the largest leaf areas, total number of leaves and final plant heights. Figure 7.8, shows the resulting plant growth in each growth media. This suggests that the best plant growth media for testing in space is soil for healthy leafy green plants. Prior to the live experiment on the ISS, all growth media was autoclaved to ensure it was free of contamination of harmful pathogens. This is an important safety step in controlling hazards for plant life and for the space station.

Figure 7.8: Comparison of Growth Mediums for Plant Species. The experiment aimed to identify the best-suited growth medium for optimal plant growth and development. Three growth media options were tested: soil, vermiculite, and soilless mixes such as hydro-gel. The results showed that soil was the best-performing medium for the tested plant species.

7.5.4 Plant species and growth media selection

The final selection of plant life was based on the results and observations from the LED wavelength and schedule testing, the plant condition after cold storage simulation and overall plant health. Kale was the selected plant life for the space-based experiment as it had the best overall performance with fast growth rates and the highest number of leaves during the LED testing. Kale also resisted issues from the cold storage simulation, it suffered with no wilting, no leaf drop and no rot. The growth media that showed the best results for leafy green plant growth was soil. The plants in the soil grew the tallest with the largest leaf areas and were a healthy green in colour., Therefore, the soil is the optimal growth medium from the types tested and is the media to be used in the space-based experiment.

7.6 Experiment box test

7.6.1 Battery lifetime test

As there is no access to USB power and the experiment has to run on battery power, the number of battery changes and astronaut interactions required had to be determined. A battery lifetime test was conducted with alkaline batteries loaded; these are the battery type available on board the ISS. All other measurement and environmental conditions were controlled as they would be in the live space-based experiment, such as sensor sampling times, LED illumination and time schedule and the temperature surrounding the box to mimic the environment on the ISS. From this test, the time to deplete a full battery pack was derived from the last timestamp recorded on the SD card, and the number of interactions was then

calculated for battery changes before depletion.

The data and corresponding timestamps were recorded for over 48 hours, with the final measurement saved at approximately 52 hours. For the entire study spanning 7 days, an interaction should happen every 48 hours and a total of 5 interactions. The first 4 interactions over the experiment trial were to introduce/change batteries and interaction 5 was to collect the SD card for data return.

7.6.2 Airtight testing

A requirement of NASA prior to any flight with this type of experiment is a contamination test to determine the experiment's waterproofing and hermetic sealing. The test exposes any transfer from the contents of the experiment to the ISS environment, assuring safety is maintained on board. The experiment at level one containment state is submerged in water and a measure of pressure or air bubble formation at the surface of the water highlights the presence of seepage or other defects in the sealing of the experiment. Experiments with electronic hardware outside level one containment have to undergo a separate approved test.

The experiment box was completely sealed up to the level one containment stage, including the CO₂ gas sensor within. The separate approved experiment entails activating the experiment CO₂ gas sensor and flooding the experiment box environment with CO₂ gas, the sensor then detects and records the levels in ppm inside the box over a 10-minute interval. The standard CO₂ parts per million are around 400 ppm and any significant spikes in levels indicate a leak has developed and a non-hermetically sealed experiment box.

7.6. EXPERIMENT BOX TEST

Time (minutes)	Temperature (C)	Relative humidity (%)	Unfiltered CO ₂ (ppm)	Filtered CO ₂ (ppm)
12:53:33	23.61	51.52	941	883
12:54:33	23.65	51.42	915	898
12:55:33	23.71	51.29	910	875
12:56:33	23.76	51.20	910	949
12:57:33	23.80	51.10	888	885
12:58:34	23.83	51.00	878	875
12:59:34	23.83	51.00	888	838
13:00:34	23.86	51.00	888	839
13:01:34	23.89	50.90	889	924
13:02:34	23.90	50.90	869	883
13:03:34	23.92	50.90	857	851

Table 7.3: CO₂ Gas leak testing Results: A 10-minute test was performed to track CO₂ levels in parts per million inside the sealed experiment box.

Figure 7.9: The sealed experiment box with CO₂ gas sensor. The sensor tracked CO₂ levels in parts per million inside the box over a 10-minute test time to ensure a hermetically sealed environment.

Due to respiration and expired CO₂ at the time of packaging, CO₂ levels were raised to a new baseline for the test of 900 ppm. The data captured, shown in Table 7.3 and Figure 7.9, demonstrates the levels observed over the 10-minute interval. The filtered CO₂ data is generated by applying a specific algorithm to smooth out variations and noise in the raw unfiltered sensor data. The level of both filtered and unfiltered CO₂ remains consistent and does not spike when CO₂ gas is introduced. The results from the approved test ensure no issues with leaking from the box and that the level-one containment measures are sufficient.

7.7 Earth-based 7-day trial

The experiment hardware will be destroyed at the end of the space-based trial and has no potential to be returned for further testing. However, simulating the conditions on the ISS and running an earth-based control is a valid way to compare the effects of space on plant growth and development. As the experiment is packaged and sealed on earth, the CO₂ and RH are representative of what each of the levels will be in space. Both the LED wavelengths and scheduling is identical to what the space plant experiment will experience. The temperature aboard should be maintained between 18 – 26°C, the earth-based experiment was kept within this range. The ultimate aim of this Earth control experiment is to test all hardware and that the autonomous system works to control the different sub-systems and records all necessary data that can be analysed elsewhere. Also, to ensure there are no issues that would compromise the safety of the ISS or threaten the safety of the crew who will be carrying out interaction event activities. The control trial establishes a baseline for the study and is a reference point to be compared with. Figures 7.13, 7.12, 7.10 and 7.11 show the results of

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baseline testing. The timestamped data collected from all of the sensors act as a benchmark for comparison between the trials conducted with similar conditions and to evaluate the success of the space experimentation. The evaluation of the two trials will give insights and indicate the plant growth and development in microgravity.

Figure 7.10: Figure showing the results of an earth-based control experiment simulating the conditions of the ISS. The graph displays the filtered CO₂ levels versus the time elapsed in days.

Figure 7.11: Figure showing the results of an earth-based control experiment simulating the conditions of the ISS. The graph displays the unfiltered CO₂ levels versus the time elapsed in days.

Figure 7.12: Figure showing the results of an earth-based control experiment simulating the conditions of the ISS. The graph displays the temperature levels versus the time elapsed in days.

Figure 7.13: Figure showing the results of an earth-based control experiment simulating the conditions of the ISS. The graph displays the RH levels versus the time elapsed in days.

7.8 Conclusion

In conclusion, the considerations and constraints of Space-based research have been evaluated, with the top priority being the safety of the crew and space station. After this, the consideration of crew schedule, equipment, and conditions on board to facilitate the plant growth experiment have been considered. The experiment construction plan has been investigated with the conditions for module size, and strict testing requirements set by NASA have been incorporated into the final design. The design has also considered the limited power resources and the need for interaction activities every 48 hours. The plant species and growth media have been selected and tested in similar conditions that will be experienced on board the ISS, as well as the potential cold storage for up to 28 days. The plant hardiness testing resulted in the Kale plant species and soil as the growth medium being selected for the space-based trials. To find issues with the final design, plant species and growth medium before launch, an Earth-

7.8. CONCLUSION

based 7-day trial was conducted, and the data collected was used as a benchmark for comparison and to evaluate the ISS experimentation with the aim to compare both sets of results for insights and impacts of plant growth and development in microgravity on the ISS.

Chapter 8

Space-based 7-day trial

8.1 Introduction

Within this chapter, the transport and launching of the experiment from Wallops Flight Facility (WFF) are detailed. The module capture and experiment setup are covered, and the results obtained from the Space-based experiment are explored.

8.2 Set-up for launch

The experiment launch is from a NASA launch site based on the Eastern Shore of Virginia, USA – NASA WFF (159). The site was first formed in 1945 and since then successfully launched over 16,000 crafts including unmanned cargo missions and both suborbital and orbital payloads. WFF is equipped with a master control centre, several large runways leading to launch pads, as well as optical tracking systems, weather tracking and prediction systems and advanced communication centres. Onsite are also

research and development labs to analyse launches and spacecraft for failures. The Wallops Island Facility is also a hub for science and education with a range of materials for scientists and engineers.

8.2.1 Experiment set up at Wallops Island

The experiment box, including all sensing equipment, LED lighting, growth chamber and plant pillow, was flown to the US where it was then hand-carried to the WFF island and set up to be tested and loaded onto a spacecraft destined for the ISS. The Kale plants were carefully transplanted into the plant pillows following the procedure outlined in Chapter 7. The plant pillows are designed to support the plant and its roots, provide a water and food source for the growing plant life and act as an anchoring point in microgravity. The plant pillow was then loaded into the plant growth chamber and secured into the experiment box with 3D-printed struts and supports. The experiment was then sealed and in line with NASA requirements underwent an approved airtightness test, as well as functionality and baselining tests. The test was successful and is crucial in ensuring there is no contamination in the space station environment. When deemed safe, the experiment was loaded into the NASA Commercial robotic resupply spacecraft Cygnus Northrop Grumman 18 (NG-18) rocket for launch to the ISS (160).

8.2.2 Functionality and baseline test prior to loading for launch

Prior to loading onto the NG-18 rocket, a functionality and baselining test is performed. The tests are critical to the space-based study. The functionality test checks all equipment, hardware and sub-systems are performing as they should and the baselining study records the starting experiment environment for the plant growth study. The functionality test comprises of checking the integrity of the experiment box visually, a test of the mechanical and electrical components, such as the LED lighting, CO₂, temperature and humidity sensors, data logger and SD card, to ensure they are functioning as expected. An observational check on the LED lighting is performing and switching as it should is also performed and of the LEDs in “night” mode. The baselining testing establishes a benchmark of the initial conditions within the experiment box once it has been sealed and airtightness tested. The test includes recording the levels of temperature, humidity, and CO₂ and in what state the lighting schedule will begin. This is also a check to make sure levels are appropriate for optimised plant growth throughout the experiment

Table 8.1 and Figures 8.1, 8.2, 8.4, 8.3 provide data on temperature, RH, unfiltered CO₂, and filtered CO₂ at intervals of time. The sampling time for the experiment has been investigated to preserve battery power but maintain quantifiable data, the resulting period of 60 s balances both concerns. The experiment begins from minute 0 when activated. The functionality and baselining sensor ran for 35 minutes and resulting data is collected for Temperature, RH, Unfiltered CO₂ and Filtered CO₂:

Temperature: At time 0, the temperature is around 24°C, over the trial the temperature climbs to around 26°C. This gradual increase is in line with

8.2. SET-UP FOR LAUNCH

Time (minutes)	Temperature (C)	Relative humidity (%)	Unfiltered CO_2 (ppm)	Filtered CO_2 (ppm)
0	24.19	66.97	1448	1448
1	24.38	64.98	1351	1361
2	24.57	63.56	1235	1287
3	24.76	63.63	1362	1311
4	25.01	64.09	1328	1306
5	25.28	63.96	1318	1326
6	25.52	63.54	1268	1302
7	25.72	62.91	1324	1296
8	25.9	62.38	1287	1291
9	26.05	61.89	1274	1288
10	26.2	61.46	1309	1245
...

Table 8.1: Functionality and baseline test results pre-launch. The tests show that the experiment is functioning and acts as a baseline for the experiment conditions.

Figure 8.1: Results of the relative humidity baseline and functionality test performed pre-launch.

the conditions surrounding the experiment box and indicated the temperature sensor, data recording of temperature and SD card storing of the data are working correctly.

8.2. SET-UP FOR LAUNCH

Figure 8.2: Results of the temperature baseline and functionality test performed pre-launch.

Figure 8.3: Results of the unfiltered CO₂ baseline and functionality test performed pre-launch.

Relative humidity: At time 0, the RH begins at 66%, over the trial the RH drops down to 60%. This is an ideal starting RH for leafy green plants and confirmation the sensor is functioning and recording timestamped data.

Figure 8.4: Results of the filtered CO₂ baseline and functionality test performed pre-launch.

Unfiltered and Filtered CO₂: At time 0, the Unfiltered and Filtered CO₂ both start at 1448 and over the course of the test trial decrease and stabilise to 1250 . This is slightly raised from ambient levels due to expired CO₂ levels when packaging and sealing. However, the packaged level is within the optimal CO₂ level for healthy plant growth and development.

The individual plant heights were recorded and positioned within the experiment box prior to sealing the box for transport. Due to the one-level containment at all times on the ISS, it was not possible to measure post-trial, only crew images and videos can be used.

The plant height prior to launch and at time of experiment box sealing is recorded as in the table below. Note, the one level of containment means it is not possible to get a post experiment comparison other than images taken on board.

The pre-launch checks are critical in experiment reliability and success

8.2. SET-UP FOR LAUNCH

Plant number (1-6)	Height (cm)
1	6.4
2	6.4
3	5.9
4	6.0
5	5.9
6	6.1

Table 8.2: Measurements of plant height prior to experiment sealing and final launch.

as this is the starting point of the space-based experiment. All pre-launch experiment checks and testing were approved, and all equipment functioned as it should.

8.3 Launch and module capture

After all testing stages are completed the experiment box was given 24 hours for the newly transplanted kale into the plant pillow time to recuperate and begin to acclimatise. After the 24-hour period, the plant was then loaded onto the NG-18 robotic resupply spacecraft, named the S.S. Sally Ride. The scheduled lift-off was delayed by a further 24 hours giving the kale more time to adapt before launch. The experiment was then successfully launched in the NG-18 spacecraft on the 7th of November 2022 at 10:32:42 AM and embarked on the spaceflight journey to the ISS. As part of the space journey, the spacecraft uses a propulsion system to change orientation and make course corrections to match the position of the ISS. A small failure meant that a solar array did not deploy as expected, this had no major effect on the journey to the ISS. Upon reaching the ISS, the craft must go through the docking process, where the craft manoeuvres with precise control and a robotic arm, operated by the crew, reaches from the ISS to align the spacecraft to the dock on the ISS, this is termed module capture. After the docking procedure, the experiment was unloaded and transferred to the dedicated experiment zone where it is attached and activated at day 0, minute 0 in space.

8.3.1 Experiment set-up on ISS

NASA Astronaut Nicole A. Mann (Col, U.S. Marine Corps), pictured in Figure 8.5, oversaw all the plant growth experiment interaction events and activities on board the ISS for this study. The first interaction event takes place on day 0 and was the initial battery installation into the plant experiment at the level one containment stage. This was successful and confirmed

8.3. LAUNCH AND MODULE CAPTURE

by the magenta glow of the red and blue LEDs, this is also an indication the experiment has the power to run and record throughout the trial. At this stage, the experiment has officially begun and all sensors should be functioning to collect timestamped data under a “daylight” LED schedule. The scheduled interactions planned for days 2, 4 and 6 took place as planned with battery level checks and battery pack changes. It is important these interactions take place on time to ensure the experiment has adequate power so that the data collection is correct and without major interruption. The space-based experiment trial reached the end of day 8, where the SD card was collected from the experiment box. The rest of the experiment went into a quarantine area, to be destroyed and disposed of. The SD card was returned on the SpaceX Commercial Resupply Service 26 (SpX-26) return flight and data was transferred for analysis.

Figure 8.5: NASA Astronaut Nicole A. Mann Conducting the First Battery Interaction for the Experiment aboard the ISS. The over-the-shoulder image shows astronaut Nicole A. Mann performing the initial battery integration for the plant growth experiment on the ISS. The image captures the moment when the batteries were first introduced.

8.4 Space-based testing

The data recorded over the entire trial onboard the ISS was analysed and compared with the Earth-based control trial. From the data collected during the experiment trial, the values for RH and unfiltered/filtered CO₂ levels are saturated throughout the trial. This indicates that a malfunction or issue has arisen that caused the sensors to measure maximum values. A subset of the data is shown in table 8.3.

Time (minutes)	Temperature (C)	Relative humidity (%)	Unfiltered CO ₂ (ppm)	Filtered CO ₂ (ppm)
0	10.55	99.99	5001	5001
1	10.89	99.99	5001	5001
2	11.34	99.99	5001	5001
3	11.89	99.99	5001	5001
4	12.44	99.99	5001	5001
5	12.97	99.99	5001	5001
6	13.51	99.99	5001	5001
7	13.96	99.99	5001	5001
8	14.44	99.99	5001	5001
9	14.9	99.99	5001	5001
10	15.28	99.99	5001	5001

Table 8.3: The sample data collected during the space based trial shows constant values returned for both unfiltered CO₂, filtered CO₂ and RH levels over the duration of the trial. This indicates there was a malfunction during the trial.

The malfunction only occurred on the sensors monitoring the RH and CO₂ levels during the experiment. The return and storage of saturated values suggests the experiment setup could collect data and store data within the experiment trial but the sensors themselves could not accurately measure the environment the plants were growing within. The final space-based results did not compare with the Earth-based trials, indicating the issue was the functioning of the experiment in space, after launch, module capture and set-up in the ISS. The harsh conditions experienced from launch

and transport may have placed high stress on the experiment box and had an impact on sensor functioning. The temperature sensor recorded an immediate steep increase to 31°C , followed by a steady temperature reading over the remaining time, with a final drop at the end of the trial. From the data recorded, the temperature began at 10°C and increased to around 30°C at minute 1968, this is the final data recording. The returned data is highly valuable and can be used as a base for future experimentation and to understand the thermal environment for sensors of plant life. All the sensor time series should have recorded for a total time of 10080 minutes, temperature results graphed in Figure 8.6. The failure to do so in the returned data, especially the temperature data that showed sensible results, further suggests there was a major issue with the experiment which prevented normal functioning for the entire study time.

Figure 8.6: The temperature data collected during the space-based trial shows increasing values of temperature over the duration of the trial. However, the final timestamp supports a possible malfunction that happened on board.

The consequence of the malfunctions was the data recorded was not con-

sistent with the Earth-based trials. The RH and CO₂ sensors returned saturated values and the temperature sensor returned only a fraction of the total trial time, the trial produced untrustworthy results for RH and CO₂ levels but useful information on the temperature on board. A possible explanation for the reported results from the experiment box could be condensing water vapour on the sensor optic. If the air has passed the dew point at some stage, during launch, transport, or module capture, particularly during the pressure changes or major temperature fluctuations prior to activation on Day 0. The light could have been scattered by the water condensing on the sensor, causing little or no light to reach the sensor and being interpreted as maximum measurement values. This is somewhat supported by the RH recordings. With the low recorded temperatures, it is likely this is the direct cause. Another possible cause is battery issues. If there is insufficient battery power due to the batteries themselves or the replacement of an old battery during an interaction event, then the results could have been affected. A built-in feature of the experiment was that at low power and when in “daytime” mode the LEDs would blink. This was an indication that battery power was insufficient. However, there was no LED blinking reported. This is to some extent supported by the low number of timestamped temperature readings on the SD card returned. The experiment may have also become damaged at some stage before or during the trial. This is a likely cause of the sensor malfunctioning and reporting saturated values. It is possible that in the cargo holds on the rocket or during extraction from the launch module into the ISS the unit encountered some significant damage causing the sensor issues in reading the environment during the space-based trial.

8.5 Conclusion

To conclude, the final experiment box design was transported to the WFF, where the box underwent pre-flight testing before being loaded onto the NG-18 spacecraft. The process to get the experiment to launch was a complex and delicate task that required major coordination and communication steps to be successfully launched. An airtightness test was carried out to satisfy NASA's requirements immediately prior to flight, this test was successful and the project was granted access to launch. Functionality and baselining experiments were also conducted to begin the space-based research, ensuring the mechanical and electrical components were fully functional. This also served as the initial conditions in the plant growth experiment environment. The project was successfully loaded, and the NG-18 spacecraft departed for the ISS, where the module was captured, and the experiment was deployed into the space station. This was a significant achievement. The experiment trial was then set up and led by NASA Astronaut Nicole A. Mann, who performed all interaction event activities and final disposal of hardware. Experimental results were returned for analysis and results have shown that there was a malfunction with the sensors monitoring the RH and CO₂, causing operational issues. The temperature sensor returned highly valuable and can be used as a base for future experimentation and to understand the thermal environment for sensors of plant life, broadening future possibilities of space-based agriculture.

Chapter 9

Summary and future work

In this chapter, the work carried out and described in previous chapters is summarised and an overall conclusion is presented with the possible next steps suggested.

9.1 Summary of the investigations

The studies carried out in this work span multiple areas of research, including thin film design and modelling, optical filtering, thin film sputter deposition, visible and infrared LVFs, development of a low cost HSI system utilising a visible LVF, machine learning algorithm development for plant identification and health level, thermal sensor output enhancement with an optical multilayer BBA coating, multi-gas sensor construction utilising an IR LVF, space payload considerations, development and testing, launch scheduling and space-based experimentation.

Thin film optical filter design, modelling and optimisation were carried out using Essential Macleod and TFCalc software. The deposition technique

of optimised designs was the sputter deposition method and the deposition system used was the 4000 series MicroDyn. The MicroDyn has unique capabilities in thin film filter fabrication. Proper cleaning techniques were employed to ensure the greatest quality and highest performance for thin film filters produced. Industry-standard metrology methods were used to evaluate thin film filter properties and final performances.

Visible and infrared LVF theoretical modelling were successfully deposited using microwave plasma-assisted pulsed DC magnetron sputtering. The fabricated LVFs demonstrated suitably selective pass bands in the visible and IR as well as necessary out-of-band blocking. Characterisation showed excellent agreement between modelled and deposited LVFs. These LVFs were used as the wavelength-separating method for a HSI system and a multi-gas sensor.

A focus of the study was the development of a HSI system, which utilised the visible LVF. The system developed scanned the LVF across a CMOS sensor using a custom rack and pinion design, this allowed for the generation of wavelength-separated images. The system was calibrated against emission lines from helium and hydrogen lamps and showed excellent agreement. Post-processing of images taken using machine learning algorithms identified different plant species and signs of disease with an accuracy of 88%. When compared to a high-end HSI system, the constructed imaging system had comparable performance. The novel LVF approach offered a low-cost system with a high price-to-performance ratio and opportunities to be used in aerial or unmanned monitoring applications.

Vast improvements were made on a thermal sensor using a multilayer BBA optical coating. The modelled multilayer comprised of a nonhydrogenated top layer and a hydrogenated carbon bulk layer. The deposited thin film

optical performance agreed with the theoretical model and a boost of $2.2\times$ was measured from the base membrane layer absorptance. When thermopile chips were built into single devices and tested, a 220% enhancement compared to uncoated thermopiles. The enhanced thermopiles have applications in a variety of NDIR gas sensor systems, particularly in the high demand CO_2 and CH_4 sensing markets. The investigation successfully produced enhanced thermopile detectors with specific detectivity, D^* , improving by approximately double for the BBA coated sensors. These are now commercially available for purchase.

The Mid-IR LVF was incorporated into a multigas sensor design and compared against a high-end COZIR CO_2 gas sensor for use in a space-based plant monitoring study. Results of the comparison show the GSS COZIR sensor has extended battery life, lower detection levels and higher sensitivity to CO_2 level change. This sensor was the one chosen for space experimentation.

All major concerns and constraints were presented and considered in the design of a space-based plant monitoring experiment. Plant “hardiness” experiments were valuable in determining the plant species suited to the harsh conditions with measurable growth and development in space. The design of the experiment box accounted for the limited space and power resources, as well as the monitoring equipment and LED lighting schedule system. The constructed experiment box was then subjected to NASA pre-launch testing and deemed fit for launch, transport and set up on board the ISS.

The experiment was launched on NG-18 rocket from WFF, and the resupply mission was successful in module capture and unloaded into the ISS. This marked a huge milestone in the project, figures 9.1 and 9.2 show the

9.1. SUMMARY OF THE INVESTIGATIONS

experiment experiencing microgravity at the time of set up and immediately prior to disposal. During the space-based trial, the RH and CO₂ sensors suffered operational issues however the temperature sensor data was returned and provides extremely valuable information on the thermal conditions on board for future experiments on the ISS and space-based agriculture.

Figure 9.1: Experiment module containing the experiment box and plant life, with the view of Earth in the background.

Figure 9.2: Experiment module final image before disposal, with SD card removed to be returned and analysed on Earth.

9.2 Project aims and goals

1. To investigate the potential of using CO₂ gas sensing and hyperspectral imaging for monitoring plant life.

The aim has been achieved. The investigation studied the monitoring of plant life through hyperspectral imaging for the identification of plant species and detection of disease or ill health and CO₂ gas sensing, combined with temperature and RH sensing, to understand the environment around the growing plant life. All sensors used have proven valuable in the study of monitoring plant life.

2. To study the impact on plant growth with finite CO₂ concentration.

The aim has been achieved. Within both the Earth-based experiment and the Space-based experiment the plant life was packaged with limited CO₂. The plant life was monitored throughout the trials and showed growth in the finite CO₂ conditions.

3. To develop a real-time monitoring system that can provide information about the plant's growth and development, to optimise the conditions for long-duration space missions.

The aim has been achieved. A real-time sensor experiment system was developed to sample the plant life environment, providing details about the growth conditions. This could be very valuable on long-haul space missions for instantaneous measurement. The built-in data storage system could be useful to look at seasonal, periodic or longer-term trends in the information captured relating to plant growth or issues with harvesting.

4. To use machine learning algorithms to analyse the data collected, to extract useful information about the plants' health levels and growth.

The aim has been achieved. The HSI system post-processing employed machine learning techniques to analyse individual pixel information contained within images, beyond the limits of the human eye. This gives a deeper understanding of the plant's health and growth,

as well as disease spread and allows for plant identification.

5. To compare the results obtained on the ISS with those obtained from a similar control experiment on Earth, to understand the effect of environmental conditions on plant growth.

The aim has been achieved. The Space-based experiment was compared with the Earth-based control and there was a malfunctioning issue. However, the recorded data has been compared and serves as a baselining study for temperature fluctuations and to understand the thermal environment in the ISS, broadening future possibilities of space-based agriculture.

6. To test the feasibility and reliability of the developed monitoring system and evaluate the potential of using it on future long-duration space missions.

The aim has been achieved. The final system was tested for both feasibility and reliability. The thesis demonstrates the potential of using a similar system on the ISS or on long-haul space exploration missions.

The research carried out has addressed all the project aims and demonstrated systems able to monitor plant growth and development. A real-time monitoring system has been designed, constructed, and tested with Earth-based trial results showing the system is capable of sampling and logging the data recorded. The system also provided valuable information on boars the ISS in the space-based trials. A HSI system was developed using novel sputter deposited LVFs as the wavelength separation method, this was combined with machine learning algorithms for post-processing of plant images. The resulting post-analysis could determine plant species

type and the presence of disease. Overall, the systems designed and developed contribute to the field of space-based plant growth and monitoring for space station use and long-duration deep space missions.

9.3 Possible next steps and future work

The root cause of the sensor malfunction is still unknown. An investigation into sensor performance under various temperature and humidity levels to find the cause of sensor failure onboard the ISS trial. To fix any condensation issues, relating to the temperature and relative humidity conditions, a water trap mechanism or dehumidifier could be introduced into the experiment box. This could be examined to remove only excess water levels above the optimum plant growth RH percentages. An alternative solution could be to apply a hydrophobic coating to the detector used in the gas sensor within the experiment box. This would act to reduce water buildup on the sensor and extend the resistance of the gas sensor to high humidity levels. This may not have been the cause of the malfunction observed and a further examination into experiment box robustness could be performed. A detailed investigation of the box components and testing in a similar environment the box experiences during launch may highlight new issues. The power delivery method on board the ISS could be the source of sensor saturation and less-than-expected temperature time series. If the battery power was not sufficient then the experiment box may have faced issues with sampling and data logging. To overcome this, USB power may be favoured to reduce the number of interaction events and the potential for an issue to arise. This could be a backup option and only rely on USB power if there is insufficient power within the batteries to complete the experiment.

9.3. POSSIBLE NEXT STEPS AND FUTURE WORK

When the root cause of the sensor malfunction is identified and the issue is resolved, a longer-term space-based trial or a long-haul space mission could employ the improved experiment box and compare results gained from all sensors within the Earth-based results in this study.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Experiment box Wiring

diagram and Bill of Materials

Wiring Diagram

Bill of materials

Material	Quantity	SDS or Product Information Sheet Filename
L7805CV 5volt regulator	1	L7805CV 5volt regulator Form
Arduino Nano	1	Arduino Nano Form
Generic type SD card reader module with SPI connection	1	micro SD card adapter Form
DS3231 Real time clock module	1	DS3231 RTC Real Time Clock Form
logic level shifter module	1	Logic level shifter Form
CO2 sensor with UART interface	1	
HDC1080 Temperature sensor module (GY-213V-HDC1080)	1	HDC1080 Temperature sensor Form
Red LED	6, 1 used	Red LED Form
Blue LED	6, 1 used	Blue LED Form
10k resistor	2	10k resistor Form
150 ohm resistor	1	150 ohm resistor Form
68 ohm resistor	1	68 ohm resistor Form
10 uF capacitor – electrolytic standard V – 50V	1	10 uF capacitor Form
1 uF capacitor	1	1 uF capacitor Form
FQP30N06L logic level N-Channel MOSFET	2	FQP30N06L logic level N-Channel MOSFET Form
5xAA battery holder	1	Links
8GB SD card	1	Micro SD card Form
Various amounts of connecting insulated wire	2m	Insulated Wire Form
Veroboard	95x95x3mm	Veroboard Form

Gas sensor	1	
Silicon glue	100g	
Perspex	10x10x10cm	
Vermiculite	1Kg	
Nylon	10x10x10cm	
Adhesive tape	50mm x 10 meters	
Gauze	10x10x10cm	
ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene)	10x10x10cm	
Resin	10x10x10cm	
PLA (Polylactic Acid)	10x10x10cm	
PET/PETG	10x10x10cm	
Transparent Sealant Paste	100g	
Transparent Sealant Paste (2)	100g	
Micro SD card	1	

Hardware

L7805CV 5volt regulator
 Arduino Nano
 Micro SD card reader module with SPI connection
 DS3231 Real time clock module
 Logic level shifter module
 HDC1080 Temperature sensor module (GY-213V-HDC1080)
 Red LED
 Blue LED
 10k resistor x 2
 150 ohm resistor x 1
 68 ohm resistor x 1
 10 uF capacitor x 1
 1 uF capacitor x1
 FQP30N06L logic level N-Channel MOSFET x 2
 Gas sensor
 5xAA battery holder x 1
 8GB SD card x 1
 Connecting wire x1m
 Veroboard 95x95x3mm
 Micro SD card

Construction Material of the Box

Perspex 10x10x10cm
 ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene) 10x10x10cm
 Resin 10x10x10cm
 PLA (Polylactic Acid) 10x10x10cm
 PET/PETG 10x10x10cm

Sealants

Silicon glue

Adhesive tape

Transparent Sealant Paste

Transparent Sealant Paste (2)

Growth media and containment

Vermiculite

Nylon

Gauze

Soil

